

H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Monitoring Framework (2024)

Department of
Natural Resources

H2Ohio

Prepared by the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Team

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Recommended Citation:

H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program, 2024. *H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program: Monitoring Framework*. Kinsman-Costello, L.E., K. Fussell, C. Winslow, J. Kerns, O.F. Schloegel, R. Mendonça, R. Becker, T. Bridgeman, K. Doro, S. J. Jacquemin, L. Johnson, G. Liu, K. McCluney, H. Michaels, W.R. Midden, S. Newell, M. Back, L. Brown, I. Rahman, and Z. Swan. Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network (LEARN) for the Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR). Columbus, OH, USA.

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1 Executive Summary

1.1 Wetland Monitoring Program Goals and Approach

The Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR) has contracted the Wetlands and Water Quality group within the Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network (LEARN) to develop and implement the *H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program*. The goal of the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program is to assess nutrient removal of wetland restoration and enhancement projects implemented by the ODNR as part of Governor Mike DeWine’s statewide H2Ohio Initiative. Although reductions in phosphorus (P) loads are the primary focus of policies aimed at mitigating harmful algal blooms (HABs) in the western basin of Lake Erie, nitrogen (N) loads also influence the size and toxicity of HABs in Lake Erie and other vulnerable water bodies throughout Ohio. Therefore, the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program incorporates assessments of both P and N removal function.

ODNR-implemented *Wetland Projects* are diverse and numerous. Some Projects have easily monitorable inflows and outflows, while many feature complex hydrology with various connections to the watershed, and many consist of multiple ecosystem units under the same Project. To create a unified framework to incorporate the diversity and quantity of Projects, the present *Monitoring Framework* consists of six chapters that provide scientific rationale and programmatic guidance.

The **Overview** chapter describes the Program’s guiding principles and administration, and the **Background: Wetlands and Water Quality** chapter details the scientific concepts that frame the Monitoring Program. All common monitoring activities are conducted by university-based researchers. As of June 2024, the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program consists of Principal Investigators and full or part-time field, lab, and administrative staff across six institutions (Bowling Green State University, Heidelberg University, Kent State University, The Ohio State University, University of Toledo, and Wright State University).

The **Monitoring Goals: Nutrient Function Measurements and Indices** chapter describes the monitoring approach of the Program and considers spatial scale and extent. The intensive data needs for conclusive nutrient removal assessment present a challenge when faced with limited resources. The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program takes a tiered approach. A relatively small number of representative *Focal Projects* (8 Projects as of June 2024) are monitored intensively to estimate all major *nutrient budget* components and directly calculate nutrient load removal. Researchers aim to use knowledge gained from Focal Projects to optimize the efficiency and validity of monitoring other Projects. Labor-intensive mechanistic approaches are deployed at select Focal Projects, including sediment-surface water nutrient exchange measurements, groundwater monitoring, plant community surveys, soil geophysical mapping, and hydrodynamic modeling. *Non-focal Projects* are monitored in a distributed way, with fewer samples collected. Generally, water and soil samples are collected from Non-focal Projects to assess *indicators* of nutrient removal function that demonstrate directional change in nutrient removal function.

1.2 Wetland Monitoring Program Data Collection

The Monitoring Program categorizes and characterizes Projects using a descriptive, attribute- and hydrologic-based approach, and *Project Specific Monitoring Plans* are developed to guide data collection for each monitored Project, the workflows for which are detailed in the **Project-Specific Monitoring** chapter. The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program aims to collect the following data to directly support the assessment of nutrient removal.

In all monitored Projects:

- Soil characteristics and nutrient status.
- Surface water nutrient concentrations.
- Hydrologic features and dynamics, including water level in areas of standing water.

In Focal Projects and select Non-focal Projects:

- Surface water flow at monitorable inflows and outflows.
- 3-D hydrodynamic models to develop accurate calculations of nutrient loads.
- Bathymetric and elevation surveys to support hydrologic monitoring and modeling.
- Soil geophysical characteristics to support mapping wetland soil patches, guide sampling efforts and scale up point-based measurements to whole ecosystem mass balance estimations.
- Groundwater wells to assess the quantity of water exchange and nutrient fluxes between wetland surface water and groundwater.
- Dominant vegetation patch mapping and vegetation tissue nutrient storage to estimate the contribution of plant uptake and storage to nutrient budgets.
- Unmanned autonomous vehicle (drone) imagery to support plant community and water inundation extent mapping.
- *In situ* stacked resin bags and *ex situ* intact core incubations to measure nutrient exchange and denitrification rates.
- Sedimentation accumulation rates to estimate the amount of nutrients stored in newly deposited wetland sediments.

1.3 Wetland Monitoring Program Data Management and Reporting

The data collection by the Monitoring Program is supported by a system that provides data centralization and assures quality and consistency so that data can be used in a timely manner. The **Data Management and Quality Control** chapter describes data entry, quality management, storage, and sharing. The Program aims to publicly release data annually alongside or shortly following the publication of the *H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Annual Report*, in a staggered timeframe that balances the urgency of the information need with the rigor of scientific assessment. In general, the annual report will summarize the previous year's data, and the dataset will be publicly available within approximately two years of data collection via an embargoed data release.

2 Overview

This chapter of the Monitoring Framework summarizes the context of the H2Ohio Initiative and Ohio Department of Natural Resources' Wetland Program. It describes the Wetland Monitoring Program's guiding principles and administration, including the Program's adaptive approach, structure and personnel, and reporting and communication tools.

Ohio is a water-rich state. However, communities throughout Ohio face water quality issues, including harmful algal blooms (HABs) on Lake Erie, the Ohio River, and numerous inland lakes. HABs threaten the health of Ohioans and negatively impact tourism, outdoor recreation, real estate, and businesses that rely on clean water. Through Governor Mike DeWine's proposed *H2Ohio initiative*, the Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR), the Ohio Environmental Protection Agency (OEPA), the Ohio Department of Agriculture (ODA), and the Ohio Lake Erie Commission (OLEC), are collaborating to address critical water quality challenges. In July 2019, the Ohio General Assembly invested \$172 million in the H2Ohio initiative, and in July 2023, \$270 million was committed to the H2Ohio initiative in the 2023–2025 biennium state budget.

The focus of H2Ohio for the ODNR began with the development of 26 *Wetland Projects* in 2020 and initially represented a \$33 million commitment to create, restore or enhance more than 3,500 acres of coastal Lake Erie and inland wetland ecosystems. As of June 2024, over 180 Wetland Projects have been initiated, with a total cumulative investment of over \$147 million. The ODNR initially prioritized Projects in northwest Ohio counties to mitigate nutrient loading rates that fuel annual HABs in the Western Lake Erie Basin. Currently, as of June 2024, Projects are distributed throughout the state to mitigate nutrient loading to local and regional water bodies, as well as the Mississippi River Basin draining into the Gulf of Mexico.

Monitoring the nutrient removal function of H2Ohio Wetland Projects is needed to evaluate success and inform management decisions, and the ODNR has partnered with the Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network (LEARN) to develop a monitoring program. The ultimate goal of the *H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program* is to assess the nutrient removal function, either directly or by evidence-based proxy, of H2Ohio Wetland Projects being implemented by the ODNR and assess Program-wide effectiveness of wetland implementation.

The core questions of the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program are:

- Is wetland restoration a cost-effective method for mitigating nutrient loads?
- How can wetland restoration and management for nutrient load reduction be effectively managed in the future?

Monitoring data supports science-based assessments of wetland restoration, construction, and management for mitigating nutrient loads. Data collected for the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program (hereafter, Monitoring Program) can support research capacity to determine how wetland characteristics (i.e., biogeochemical properties, soil characteristics, hydrological patterns, vegetative communities, location, design features, management) shape nutrient removal function over space and time. University-based researchers aim to communicate monitoring results to inform future ODNR Project decisions in order to better maximize nutrient retention.

This document, the *Monitoring Framework*, describes the guiding principles, program structure, scientific rationale, monitoring goals, data collection techniques, and data management systems for the Monitoring Program. *Project Specific Monitoring Plans* detail specific monitoring approaches and sampling designs for individual Wetland Projects. Standardized protocols are compiled in a *Field, Lab, and Computational Operations Manual* to ensure standard field, lab, computational, and data management techniques throughout the Monitoring Program. All of these documents are routinely updated within an adaptive framework.

2.1 Program Guiding Principles

The policies, structure, and operations of the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program are guided by five guiding principles:

- 1) Responsible, Open, and Sound Science
- 2) A Community of Researchers, Professionals, and Partners
- 3) Learning by Doing in an Adaptive Framework
- 4) Building a Foundation for Long-Term Monitoring
- 5) Focus on Function

2.1.1 *Responsible, Open, Sound Science*

As university researchers, we design and implement the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program from a research ethic. We value and strive for unbiased generation of knowledge and clear communication to inform decision making. Maintaining the trust of stakeholders, decision makers, and the public to whom we are accountable is of the utmost importance. We strive for open science and aim to create products that contextualize and clarify monitoring results. Monitoring decisions are driven by data collection goals, aiming for a comprehensive assessment of H2Ohio Wetland Projects within available resources. Decisions about monitoring intensity and resources are not driven by nor do they imply value or effectiveness of individual Projects.

As experts in our fields, through existing relationships with local and regional partners, and as individual citizens in our communities, we may individually inform aspects of specific H2Ohio Wetland Projects including site selection, design, and management. In addition, we may provide science-based predictions to the ODNR and other partners regarding the effectiveness of specific Projects based on design proposals. However, in our role as Monitoring Program researchers we do not endorse specific Projects or designs outside of structured proposal review requests.

2.1.2 *A Community of Researchers, Professionals, and Partners*

As a community of researchers, we value and encourage the contributions of all Monitoring Program personnel, acknowledging that diverse perspectives are necessary (Cheruvilil et al., 2014; V. H. Smith, 2003). We are committed to a Program in which all individuals are welcomed, safe, and supported. Our groups are integrated, coordinated crews working together toward a common goal. Senior personnel and leaders within the Program have a particular responsibility to ensure the safety and well-being of students and trainees when and where they work with and for the Program.

The Monitoring Program is situated within a broader community and network of agency professionals, university researchers, conservation partners, and stakeholders. We engage with these constituents through two-way conversations, listening, and mutual learning.

2.1.3 Learning by Doing in an Adaptive Framework

The Monitoring Program uses a learning-by-doing approach inspired by the process of adaptive management to iteratively evaluate our goals, framework, and approaches (Williams & Brown, 2018). Our Program is novel and as such, substantial new development is required. As we develop new strategies to assess wetlands, we are coordinating a large, multi-institutional network. An adaptive approach acknowledges that early data collection, while not perfectly optimized, generates useful information and lessons.

2.1.4 Focus on Function

Most regulatory compliance monitoring programs for wetlands are aimed primarily at assessing structural features including size, substrate type, surrounding land use, hydrologic indicators, and plant community indicators (Mack, 2001). While structural measures may indicate wetland habitat value or impairment status, they infer but do not directly measure nutrient removal functions. It is challenging to assess the “invisible” water quality functions of a wetland. There is strong evidence, based on fundamental biogeochemistry and empirical studies, that restoration of wetland structure does not necessarily indicate effective biogeochemical function (Hossler et al., 2011). Despite the common assumption that wetlands are generally effective at filtering sediments, nitrogen (N), and phosphorus (P), these drivers of eutrophication are subject to starkly contrasting chemical processes and biogeochemical mechanisms. In other words, an environment that is effective at N removal may not necessarily be effective at removing P, and vice versa.

To confidently assess the nutrient function of Projects, the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program directly measures nutrients and nutrient removal processes in wetland ecosystems through time. No widely agreed-upon criteria exist to define the success or failure of wetlands from a water quality standpoint, and it is not our intention to establish such criteria. Rather, we aim to produce quantitative, direct, or meaningful proxy measures of nutrient removal. Alongside the Monitoring Program work, we proactively facilitate coordinated, complimentary research funded by external sources for more comprehensive mechanistic studies of underlying processes to strengthen scientific understanding of nutrient removal patterns.

2.1.5 Building a Foundation for Long-Term Monitoring

Decades of research and centuries of experience and observation demonstrate that ecological systems are dynamic—no single point in time or single year can indicate the full function of an ecosystem or its trajectory (Knapp et al., 2012; Wolkovich et al., 2014). Some ecosystem processes take decades to achieve levels similar to undisturbed reference wetlands (Ballantine & Schneider, 2009).

While the Monitoring Program is collecting data early and often, we are also building a foundation to support the long-term monitoring necessary to assess wetland function that integrates over seasonal and year-to-year changes. Long-term monitoring strengthens our ability to predict how systems may behave in the future. Robust documentation of methods and standardized, consistent protocols ensures that data collected over time are accessible and usable for synthesis in the future. Sampling schemes and other data collection are planned with repeated measures over time in mind. Monitoring Program researchers intentionally consider how information can be integrated to evaluate long-term ecosystem function. Data collection to estimate annual wetland nutrient budgets can also reveal changes across seasons and in response to storm and flood events. The Monitoring Program aims to lay a foundation that can sustain monitoring of H2Ohio Wetland Projects for at least ten years. *As of June 2024, the Monitoring Program's central focus is to integrate wetland nutrient removal rates on annual time scales to be integrated over time, although other temporal periods are also evaluated.*

2.2 Program Administration

The Monitoring Program is administered under an adaptive framework that allows for iteration, flexibility, and growth. The Program is contracted by the ODNR and administered by LEARN, and the two entities have agreed upon communication methods and reporting standards, which are described in the subsections below.

2.2.1 Adaptive Framework: Learning by Doing

The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program is the first of its kind— Program researchers have engaged with wetland scientists and managers throughout the Great Lakes region and the United States during initial development, and still know of no other program monitoring the nutrient biogeochemistry of multiple diverse created, restored, and enhanced wetlands under a unified, long-term framework. As such, substantial new development has been required since the beginning of the Monitoring Program in 2020. Along with developing strategies to assess wetlands with inherently limited resources and capacity, the Monitoring Program invests in tools, workflows and staff to optimize skillsets and approaches for coordinating a large, multi-institutional network. Just as in adaptive management, the Monitoring Program is learning about a system through the process of managing it, more specifically learning about how best to design and implement a monitoring program through implementing a monitoring program.

The ONDR-implemented H2Ohio Wetland Projects, and the Monitoring Program assessing their nutrient removal function, constitute a broader scope and scale than other traditional adaptive management examples. This agency–university partnership integrates numerous management decisions because of the diversity of approaches to Project location, design, implementation, and management. It provides an opportunity to develop a more deliberative, coordinated restoration program, in which decisions can be assessed within a framework of larger, integrated goals. The Monitoring Program aims to build capacity for Program-scale assessment and management (i.e., across Wetland Projects), while empowering Project-scale decision making and management through the connections made through Project-scale data and models.

An adaptive approach acknowledges that early data collection, while not perfectly optimized, can generate valuable information and lessons. Despite the challenge of building a novel Monitoring Program from the ground up, the Monitoring Program began data collection shortly after the first H2Ohio Wetland Projects were constructed—the first projects were constructed in 2020 and 2021, and Monitoring Program data collection began preliminary in 2021 and routinely in 2022. Early data collection, often within a year after many Projects are initially constructed, provides an unprecedented opportunity to track the trajectories of these dynamic, novel ecosystems, as well as providing early information to agencies and managers.

The Monitoring Program iterates its own structure and framework in a process similar to that applied in ecosystem adaptive management (Figure 1). An adaptive framework accommodates the many layers of uncertainty inherent to environmental monitoring. *In adaptive management, “uncertainty” refers to a lack of predictability or understanding in a natural resource system. For the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program, an “uncertainty” is any lack of knowledge or understanding that limits the Program’s ability to optimize sampling effort and coordination.*

Figure 1. Illustration of how the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program’s annual adaptive cycle takes lessons from the process of adaptive management. Each year at the All-Hands Workshop (circled in purple box), researchers (1) refine the overall Wetland Monitoring Program goals if needed and (2) define/refine Wetland Monitoring Program-wide objectives for the year (to be documented in Program-wide Annual Monitoring Plan). Through discussion of (3) Project-specific objectives and (4) uncertainties, researchers (5) draft or update Project-specific Monitoring Plans. The orange boxes outside the purple circle indicate year-long implementation of the decisions made at the All-Hands Workshop, including (6) using the monitoring plans to monitor specific Projects and (7) data compilation and synthesis, all of which feed back into (8) evaluation that will occur at the following workshop.

The Monitoring Program’s adaptive cycle facilitates re-alignment of the monitoring goals and data collection techniques, with agency- and partner-defined goals and knowledge needs. An iterative approach allows researchers to refine sampling strategies to better understand the complexity of wetlands (e.g., type, size, location, etc.), which should lead to improved mechanistic understanding of the wetland functions and characteristics underlying nutrient mitigation, along with efficient use of limited resources and capacity.

2.2.2 Program Structure & Personnel

LEARN is a group of field stations, scientific laboratories and researchers examining a diverse array of topics within Ohio, working together to promote collaborative research, education, and networking to address the challenges and opportunities facing Ohio’s freshwater resources. LEARN was contracted by the ODNR to develop and implement the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program in 2020. Administratively, the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program is housed at The Ohio State University (OSU). OSU’s Office of Sponsored Programs handles subaward agreements to other universities and fiscal reporting. The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program requires a diverse set of research expertise (e.g., wetland ecology, coastal processes, hydrology, soil science), and therefore the Monitoring Program built a team of LEARN members from universities across Ohio. LEARN personnel communicates and coordinates regularly with ODNR H2Ohio Program staff (Figure 2). See **H2Ohio Wetland Projects: Project-Specific Monitoring Timelines** for details about ODNR and LEARN communication milestones throughout a given project. *The following subsection describes the leadership team, core staff and researcher crews of the Monitoring Program as of June 2024.*

Figure 2. Personnel structure (as of June 2024) of the Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR) and Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network (LEARN) that comprise the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program. The red box on the left outlines the ODNR personnel and the blue box on the right outlines the LEARN personnel.

Leadership Team and Core Staff

The *leadership team* of the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program consists of a Research Lead, two Administrative Leads, and an ODNR Agency Lead. The Research Lead is an Associate Professor and wetland scientist at Kent State University, Dr. Lauren Kinsman-Costello, who oversees all aspects of the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program development, sampling, and data analysis. The Ohio Sea Grant Director, Dr. Chris Winslow and Assistant Director, Dr. Kristen Fussell are the Executive Director and Treasurer, respectively, of LEARN. Drs. Winslow and Fussell are the Administrative and Outreach Leads on the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program and primary investigators on the grant awarded to LEARN (via Ohio Sea Grant) to fund this program. Dr. Janice Kerns, Reserve Manager for Old Woman Creek National Estuarine Research Reserve Station (OWC NERRS), is the Agency Lead for this program and serves as the liaison between LEARN and the ODNR to ensure lines of communication are open and that Monitoring Program activities are well aligned with ODNR information needs.

ODNR core staff include a Wetland Restoration Program Manager and an Assistant Wetland Restoration Program Manager, who oversee the selection of H2Ohio-funded Wetland Projects and assign each Project to a specific Project Manager from an appropriate ODNR division and office. The Wetland Restoration Program Manager (Eric Saas) and Assistant Program Manager (Rachel DeNoewer) attend regular H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program leadership meetings.

LEARN core staff include three full-time coordinators, who assist with research and administration of the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program. The Research Coordinator (Olivia Schloegel) and Chief Data Manager (Raíssa Mendonça) are supervised and mentored by the Monitoring Program Research Lead (Lauren Kinsman-Costello) and employed by the home institution of the Research Lead (Kent State University), and oversee research sampling, meeting coordination, and data management. Mackenzie Gesek, Grant and Contract Associate for Ohio Sea Grant, serves as the Administrative Coordinator and handles administrative functions of the Monitoring Program on behalf of LEARN, with additional support from Ohio Sea Grant's Aquaculture Extension Educator and LEARN Coordinator, Nicole Wright. In addition, Ohio Sea Grant's communications team periodically oversees development of outreach and education materials. As of June 2024, there are plans to hire an Outreach and Engagement Coordinator to expand partner data collection and community engagement.

University Researchers: Base and Specialist Crews

The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program personnel and tasks are organized into “crews,” led by university faculty Principal Investigators (PIs) from University of Toledo, Bowling Green State University, Heidelberg University, Kent State University, Wright State University (Figure 3). Within each crew, a full-time lead research technician is generally responsible for managing the data collected by personnel working at that institution. Lead research technicians train personnel in general data management best practices and lab-specific data management protocols, and they may delegate data management tasks to members of their research teams. Crews are in regular contact with the Research Project Coordinator.

Base Crews coordinate research and monitoring at specific Projects assigned by geography. Base crew teams plan and implement general field soil and water sampling, routine sensor maintenance, and soil and water lab analyses. *Specialty Crews* plan and implement specific tasks requiring specialized expertise, tools, and equipment across all Projects. A centralized *Coordination Crew* leads Monitoring Program development and implementation by leading collaborative decision making, ensuring progress on objectives and tasks, facilitating communication within and among Monitoring Program research crews, ODNR agency Project managers and leadership, and establishing communication with collaborating conservation partners. The Coordination Crew is responsible for developing centralized data management and ensuring standardized protocols are implemented under a unified framework, and is made up primarily of the LEARN core staff described above.

Figure 3. H2Ohio Monitoring Program Crews (as of June 2024). Base Crews (left column) coordinate research and monitoring at specific Wetland Projects assigned by geography. Specialty Crews (right column) plan and implement specific tasks requiring specialized expertise, tools, and equipment across all Projects. A centralized Coordination Crew (middle column) leads Monitoring Program development and implementation and facilitates coordination among crews. Each box represents one crew, the text indicates the geography or specialty data parameter of the crew, and the logos represent the institutions at which the crews are based.

2.2.3 Annual H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Workshop

The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program hosts an annual *All-Hands Workshop* attended by all researchers, invited agency personnel, and conservation partners, generally at the start of the calendar year. At each annual All-Hands Workshop, Monitoring Program monitoring goals and data collection objectives are re-visited and adjusted to respond to lessons learned and to align with evolving agency and decision maker needs (Figure 1).

2.2.4 Annual H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Work Plan

After periodic communication with the ODNR and H2Ohio Wetland Project partners, the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program composes a plan defining the monitoring goals and data collection objectives for the coming year. The *Annual Work Plan* includes:

- List of all H2Ohio Projects to be monitored in the following year, including indications of whether they will be monitored as Focal and Non-focal Projects, what monitoring phase and year the Project will be in (i.e., Initial Project Inquiry, Pre-Construction Characterization, Post-Construction Characterization, Routine Monitoring Year 1, 2, etc.), and which geographically designated Base Crew will lead sample collection planning and implementation.
- Descriptions of Specialty Crew data collection plans, priorities, and timeline for the year, specifying in which Projects data will be collected, as well as other major tasks, milestones, and goals.
- Overview of program-level goals and objectives, including a calendar of key benchmarks and milestones in data management, protocol refinement, coordination among monitoring crews, and data synthesis.

2.2.5 Reporting & Communications

Consistent reporting to the ODNR and communication with the public ensure accountability and align with the guiding principle of **Responsible, Open, Sound Science**. The LEARN Administrative Coordinator, Monitoring Program Research Coordinator, and Monitoring Program Chief Data Manager submit *Quarterly Administrative Progress Reports* documenting the work performed toward the tasks and deliverables indicated in the biennial contract between ODNR and LEARN. *Annual Reports* containing summaries of data and accomplishments are also submitted to the ODNR. *In 2022 and 2023, Annual Reports were based on calendar year (January to December) effort, and in the future the timeframe may be adjusted to water year (October to September).*

The Monitoring Program shares a broad overview of progress with the public each year through a *public webinar* advertised by LEARN, the Ohio Sea Grant Program, and the ODNR. Leaders from across the Program contribute to the conceptual outline and content for a presentation led by the Monitoring Program Research Lead. This update to the public is generally presented in the fall or winter and recorded for future viewing via Ohio Sea Grant. An archive of reporting and public communication materials can be found on the [LEARN website](#).

3 Background: Wetlands and Water Quality

Aligned with the guiding principle of *Responsible, Open, Sound Science*, the Monitoring Program strives to integrate and expand upon the best available wetland research to accurately assess the nutrient function of H2Ohio Wetland Projects. *This chapter of the Monitoring Framework details the scientific concepts and background information that underly the Program's data collection approach.*

3.1 Eutrophication, Wetlands, & Water Quality

Eutrophication is a persistent challenge throughout Ohio, the country, and the world. Excess nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) fuel abundant growth of nuisance and sometimes toxic algae and cyanobacteria, forming harmful algal blooms (Anderson et al., 2002; Heisler et al., 2008) and, under some conditions, low oxygen “dead zones” inhospitable to aquatic life (Carpenter et al., 1998; Wurtsbaugh et al., 2019). Recurring harmful algal blooms (HABs) in the Western Basin of Lake Erie, Grand Lake St. Marys, and many other Ohio water bodies threaten public health, harm recreation and tourism, require costly drinking water treatment infrastructure, and profoundly degrade some of Ohio's most valuable ecosystems. The economic effects of HABs can be devastating (USEPA, 2015a). A report determined that \$3.45 billion worth of property is threatened by Lake Erie HAB impacts and up to \$305 million in tourism is at risk of being lost (Bingham et al., 2015).

Decades of research have demonstrated the driving role that excess P plays in fueling HABs in freshwater ecosystems like lakes, ponds, rivers, and wetlands (Schindler, 1977). The amount of P that enters the Western Basin of Lake Erie every year, particularly inorganic P as phosphate in spring and early summer, in large part determines the severity of that year's summer bloom (Stumpf et al., 2012). Thus, policies and decision making in Ohio focus on limiting P loads to mitigate HABs (International Joint Commission, 2014).

However, N mitigation is equally important given emerging evidence supporting the role N availability plays in shaping HAB biomass and toxicity (Davis et al., 2015; Monchamp et al., 2014; Sandrini et al., 2015). It is well known that limiting N loads to marine coastal ecosystems can mitigate eutrophication and diminish blooms and “dead zones” in saltwater environments, but N also plays a major role in developing the toxic HABs in Lake Erie (Cloern, 2001; Jones, 2020; Newell et al., 2019; Tucker, 1992; Walve et al., 2021). Management efforts to reduce P pollution without simultaneously controlling N can cause nutrient imbalances in eutrophic systems, which may favor toxic cyanobacterial HABs, even those dominated by taxa that cannot fix atmospheric N₂ gas (Gobler et al., 2016). Prior to P load reductions in the 1970s, HABs in Lake Erie were mostly N₂-fixers (e.g., *Aphanizomenon* and *Dolichospermum*, formerly *Anabaena*) but now HABs are primarily non-N₂-fixing *Microcystis* and *Planktothrix* (Steffen et al., 2014). Non-N₂-fixing cyanobacteria are superior competitors for bioavailable N relative to eukaryotic taxa (Monchamp et al., 2014). The main toxins produced by *Microcystis* (and other cyanobacteria) are microcystins, which are comprised of 10 N atoms per molecule on average, and concentrations of microcystins are strongly correlated with indices of available N (Davis et

al., 2015). Generally, dual nutrient approaches aimed at simultaneously diminishing N and P loads to vulnerable ecosystems ensure the highest potential for successful long-term mitigation of eutrophication and HABs (Paerl et al., 2016, 2018).

To mitigate the widespread historical and continued loss of wetlands, particularly in Ohio, programs have incentivized the creation, restoration, enhancement, and preservation of wetlands. Considerable resources are devoted to wetlands specifically for improving water quality and removing nutrients (Verhoeven et al., 2006). When cultivated and fertilized land is converted to wetland habitat, this alone mitigates some of the nutrient inputs associated with agricultural land use. Constructed wetlands can be a cost-effective means of nutrient mitigation (Irwin et al., 2018). Constructed wetlands have been shown to remove 40–55% of total nitrogen (TN) and 40–60% total phosphorus (TP) from agricultural watersheds across different construction methods (Vymazal, 2007). However, the functional capacity of wetlands to remove polluting nutrients varies. Wetland N removal rates increase with escalating hydraulic loading rate and retention until a maximum threshold is reached, and then efficiency declines (Lin et al., 2008). Particularly, restored wetlands can exhibit limited denitrification rates and can, at times, be a source, rather than a sink, of P (Ardón et al., 2010; Kinsman-Costello et al., 2014). *The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program incorporates assessments of both P and N removal function.*

3.2 Wetland Hydrology: Water Sources & Connectivity Matter

As a unique hydrologic feature of the landscape, wetlands are transitional between terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems (USEPA, 2008). Water transports energy and nutrients to and from wetlands through precipitation, surface runoff, streams and rivers, groundwater, and tides (Mitsch & Gosselink, 2015). The nature of a wetland's hydrologic connection to the landscape shapes its structure, while the relative proportion of water sources defines a wetland's chemistry.

Landscape connectivity determines a wetland's potential to contribute to landscape-scale nutrient removal (Cohen et al., 2016; Golden et al., 2019). For example, a precipitation-fed bog that has no significant inflow or outflow of surface water or groundwater likely contributes a negligible amount to the cycling of N and P within a larger watershed. On the other hand, a riparian or drainage and treatment wetland that is fed by a stream, ditch, or other surface water flow, can interact with water that carries nutrients from sources within the watershed, and thus offers the potential to transform and remove harmful nutrients the water carries. In reality, the water dynamics of many wetlands are complex combinations of inflows and outflows. Often, wetland connections are controlled directly by human management using levees, dikes, pumps, and water level control structures. In addition to the direct biogeochemical retention and processing of nutrients in wetlands, adding wetlands to watersheds can influence net nutrient loads solely through their impact on landscape hydrology (Cohen et al., 2016). When appropriately located, wetlands can reduce peak flows, enhance infiltration, and limit erosion, all of which may indirectly mitigate nutrient loads.

Three critical hydrologic variables can together be used to describe a wetland's hydrologic regime: water levels, hydroperiod, and residence time (Mitsch & Gosselink, 2015). Water level refers to the general elevation of wetland water surface relative to the soil or land surface. Hydroperiod describes the temporal variability (timing, duration) of wetland water levels. Residence time is a measure of the average time that water remains in a wetland and is calculated by the ratio of the volume of water within the wetland to the rate of flow through the wetland. *The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program assesses the hydrology of each monitored Wetland Project using a combination of field measurements, continuously logging sensors, spatial data, and modeling to track variables over time to characterize the hydrologic regime of Project wetlands, as built or modified, and to calculate nutrient mass loads where possible.*

3.3 Wetland Vegetation and Nutrient Cycling

Vegetation plays important roles in nutrient cycling. The most direct influence of plants on nutrients is by uptake and storage in tissues (Peterjohn & Correll, 1984; Tyler et al., 2012; Vymazal & Březinová, 2018). As plant tissues senesce and decompose, these organic nutrient forms may be buried or may be re-mineralized to bioavailable inorganic forms (Nichols, 1983; Reddy et al., 1999). Nutrient storage can be prolonged in perennial and woody vegetation. Plant nutrient uptake can meaningfully contribute to mitigating eutrophication when plants take up and store labile nutrients in seasons when nutrients contribute to algal blooms (Risgaard-Petersen & Ottosen, 2000). Additionally, plants alter physicochemical conditions that influence nutrient cycling. For instance, plant roots may add oxygen to otherwise anoxic soils or plants may physically trap sediment (Hupfer & Dollan, 2003; Reddy et al., 1989; Vymazal & Březinová, 2018). Plants also may add organic matter, either via senesced tissues or via root exudates, and this can both increase the nutrient retention capacity of the soil and stimulate the activity of microbes important in nutrient cycling. *The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program aims to map dominant functional plant taxa in restoration Projects and directly measure N and P content of select plant taxa and tissues to estimate the contribution of plant uptake and storage to nutrient budgets.*

3.4 Nutrient Biogeochemistry

Wetlands are highly dynamic biogeochemical systems that are potentially powerful at nutrient removal (Kadlec & Wallace, 2008; Reddy & DeLaune, 2008). There are important differences in N and P cycling processes in wetlands. The inherent chemical properties of N and P pose biogeochemical trade-offs that challenge wetland design, construction, and maintenance for effective removal of both nutrients simultaneously. Wetland restoration for nutrient removal remains inadequately informed because of remaining knowledge gaps regarding nutrient biogeochemistry. This critical biogeochemical understanding is then sometimes poorly communicated to practitioners implementing wetlands for nutrient management. *The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program is therefore designed to assess specific, dominant nutrient removal mechanisms, which are often distinct for P and N.*

3.4.1 Phosphorus

In the environment, P exists in two major chemical forms: the inorganic phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) ion and P covalently bonded in organic molecules of living and dead biomass, hereafter referred to as organic P (Figure 4). In practice, P is often delineated not only by its chemical form but by size fraction, with “dissolved” P typically referring to the operationally defined P-containing material that passes through a 0.45 μm filter, and “particulate” P as the larger material that can be composed of any combination of these chemical forms (Figure 5). Soluble reactive phosphorus (SRP), which is the fraction of dissolved P that reacts with a colorimetric molybdate reagent is routinely used to indicate PO_4^{3-} concentrations (Murphy & Riley, 1962).

Wetlands diminish P load to downstream ecosystems through three main mechanisms: long-term storage through sedimentation of P-bearing particles, PO_4^{3-} sorption to soil minerals, and plant uptake (Figure 4, Figure 6). The relative capacity and permanence of each of these mechanisms vary and, in some cases, wetlands can become net sources of P, rather than net sinks (Ardón et al., 2010; Kinsman-Costello et al., 2014). The majority of net removal and long-term storage of P by wetlands occurs through the accretion and burial of particulate P, generally sedimentation of P-bearing particles (Noe et al., 2019; Richardson et al., 1996). PO_4^{3-} sticks readily to mineral surfaces, especially metal oxides, by geochemical associations including sorption and ion exchange, but the proportion of P removal that can be attributed to PO_4^{3-} sorption is typically smaller in magnitude than particulate P storage (Noe et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2013). In addition, this relatively small, but highly ecologically relevant proportion of sorbed inorganic soil P may be released from sediments and soils if conditions alter the sorption–desorption equilibrium (Noe et al., 2013). Plants and other organisms assimilate and store P in their biomass, which represents a storage pool of variable duration and transforms available inorganic P into less available organic P forms. *The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program aims to use a variety of measurements to directly assess the net removal of P and the relative importance of biological and geochemical P-removal processes in select intensively monitored Wetland Projects and develop meaningful proxies and models to estimate or predict P removal in less intensively monitored Projects.*

Figure 4. A combination of biological and geochemical processes control phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) bioavailability and mobility. Plants and microbes can directly take up PO_4^{3-} , converting inorganic P to organic P forms. Organic P is mineralized to PO_4^{3-} via microbial decomposition. The PO_4^{3-} ion is geochemically reactive to many soil minerals and can sorb strongly to iron and aluminum oxides and can co-precipitate with calcium carbonates. The strength of the sorption–desorption equilibrium with metal oxides depends on metal redox forms, mineral structure, and soil pH conditions.

Figure 5. Schematic depicting typical detection of phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) in environmental water samples. Phosphorus (P) in water samples is typically detected as “soluble reactive phosphate” (SRP) using an established colorimetric method (Murphy & Riley, 1962). Samples are filtered prior to SRP analysis to measure dissolved PO_4^{3-} , chemically digested to detect total P, and filtered and chemically digested to measure total dissolved P.

Figure 6. Conceptual diagram illustrating the dominant phosphorus (P) removal mechanisms in wetlands. Wetlands can remove P by three major mechanisms: plant uptake and tissue storage, geochemical association of phosphate with sediment minerals (e.g., sorption to iron oxides), and long-term storage by sedimentation and burial. None of these processes permanently remove P from an ecosystem, and stored P may be re-released and exported downstream as plant tissues senesce and mineralize, associated phosphate is released from sediment minerals, and particulate P is resuspended and transported in surface waters.

Many useful soil-scale indices of P sorption capacity, soil P storage potential, and soil P release vulnerability have been developed to assess PO_4^{3-} sorption-desorption processes that contribute to wetland P cycling. Many of these indices are based on multi- or single-point phosphate sorption assays aimed at estimating isotherms to describe soil phosphate sorption characteristics and then relate these characteristics to independent measures of soil geochemistry (e.g., pH), especially the content of highly sorptive poorly crystalline iron and aluminum minerals (Bache and Williams, 1971; Froelich, 1988; Nair et al., 2015). A large body of research from agronomy, soil science, and aquatic ecology demonstrates that the capacity of a given soil to sorb PO_4^{3-} depends both on the amount of PO_4^{3-} in the soil as well as the amount and mineral structure of sorptive iron and aluminum oxide minerals (Wang et al. 2013), with pH and redox conditions shaping the strength of geochemical association between PO_4^{3-} and mineral oxides (Stumm & Morgan, 1996). The Mehlich-3 extraction was originally developed as an index of crop plant-available PO_4^{3-} , adapted to allow for simultaneous measurement of soil components that influence PO_4^{3-} availability including Fe, Al, and Ca (Pierzynski, 2000). A PO_4^{3-} sorption capacity index based on ratio of Mehlich-3 extractable P to Mehlich-3 extractable Fe and Al, known as Soil Phosphorus Storage Capacity (SPSC), has been used in the Great Lakes region and other areas to assess soil capacity to sequester and/or release P for the purposes of prioritizing sites for wetland restoration (Nair et al., 2015; VanZomeren & Berkowitz, 2020).

3.4.2 Nitrogen

Nitrogen cycling in wetlands is dominated by microbially mediated processes that transform the chemical form of N (Figure 7) which dictates whether the N remains in the system in plant and animal biomass, is lost as a gas, or moves downstream and contributes to nutrient pollution (Reddy & DeLaune, 2008). Plant uptake contributes to both short- and long-term net N storage (Jeke et al., 2019; Maltais-Landry et al., 2009). Upon entering a wetland, nitrate (NO_3^-) may be taken up by plant roots or leached into groundwater, but under anoxic conditions, microbes transform NO_3^- into the nitrogenous gases nitrous oxide (N_2O) and nitrogen (N_2) through denitrification (Figure 8). This leads to a net permanent removal of available N from the landscape system to the atmospheric system. Under optimal conditions, the end product of denitrification is N_2 , a harmless and inert gas. However, under periods of varying water saturation and oxygen availability, which cause fluctuating redox conditions, denitrification can produce the harmful greenhouse gas N_2O as a terminal product (Burgin et al., 2013).

Alternatively, NO_3^- can be recycled back to ammonium (NH_4^+) through dissimilatory nitrate reduction (DNRA), in which case available N remains in the system rather than being removed, with the potential to further contribute to eutrophication (Burgin & Hamilton, 2007). The balance between these processes is largely controlled by redox conditions, organic carbon and NO_3^- availability, as well as the presence of sulfide. Ammonium and urea can also be converted to NO_3^- through microbial nitrification and subsequently lost through denitrification or recycled through DNRA. Wetland soils and the microbial communities that reside in them are powerful transformers of NO_3^- . However, the interactions between pathways are complex, so the ultimate products of their transformations, and thus the fate of excess N and contribution to downstream eutrophication depend on soil chemical and physical conditions (Burgin & Hamilton, 2007). *The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program aims to measure N forms in water, soils, and plant material to assess the impacts of H2Ohio Wetland Projects on mitigating N loads to downstream ecosystems.*

Figure 7. The nitrogen (N) cycle is characterized by numerous microbially mediated redox transformations of N among its many chemical forms and oxidation states. From the perspective of water quality, complete denitrification, in which nitrate is converted to inert nitrogen gas (N_2) is the optimal N removal mechanism. Yellow arrows indicate oxidation reactions, red arrows are reduction reactions, and white arrows indicate no redox change.

Figure 8. Conceptual diagram illustrating the dominant nitrogen removal mechanisms in wetlands. Nitrogen commonly enters wetland systems as nitrate (NO_3^-) from surface runoff. In addition to removal via plant uptake and settling and burial, wetland removal of N via complete denitrification – conversion of NO_3^- to the inert nitrogen gas (N_2) – is the optimal N removal pathway as it exports N to the atmosphere. However, incomplete denitrification and turnover of particulate N can release readily available forms of N (e.g., NH_4^+) that can be exported to downstream systems.

3.5 Nutrient Legacies of Agricultural Land Use

The agricultural land use and drainage that characterizes large areas of Ohio leaves legacies long after cultivation activities cease and wetland hydrology is restored (Hamilton, 2012; Stackpoole et al., 2019). In historically drained and cultivated land, accumulated fertilizer PO_4^{3-} that was never used by plants can be released into surface waters when wetland hydrology is restored (Kinsman-Costello et al., 2014). In a given year, cultivated plants typically take up and incorporate about 20% of PO_4^{3-} added as fertilizer and a portion of the unutilized fertilizer P accumulates in soils, contributing to legacy P (Sattari et al., 2012; Syers et al., 2008; Wolf et al., 1987). Estimates of the duration of sediment P release in restored wetlands range from 10 to 100 years (Ardón et al., 2010; Hamilton, 2012).

Similarly, due to its mobility, NO_3^- accumulates in groundwater. A study by the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) of streams that drain into the Chesapeake Bay estimated that if agricultural sources of NO_3^- were lowered in the watershed, a reduction in stream NO_3^- concentration would not be observed for at least a decade (Lindsey et al., 2003). Thus, groundwater accumulation of N can limit restoration activities throughout a watershed wherever restored aquatic ecosystems interact with the water table. *Many H2Ohio Wetland Projects involve restoration of wetland hydrology to formerly drained agricultural land and the Monitoring Program expects that their nutrient retention and removal capacity may be shaped by this prior land use.*

Wetland loss is a defining feature of the midwestern United States, particularly in Northwest Ohio where the historic Great Black Swamp was drained to create fertile cultivated farmland (Dahl, 1990; Kaatz, 1955). But alongside this history of drainage and loss, Ohio has been a leader in wetland restoration. The Olentangy River Wetland Research Park at The Ohio State University was the site of important early work demonstrating the capacity of wetlands to filter polluting nutrients (Nairn & Mitsch, 1999). Thus, it is fitting that Ohio takes the lead in developing an improved approach to assessing the effectiveness of wetlands at nutrient removal. *Not only does information generated by the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program support assessment of the success of state investments in wetland ecosystem infrastructure, but it can serve as a foundation on which to build innovative research in wetland science.*

3.6 Wetland Ecosystem Services: Trade-offs, Bundles & Synergies

In addition to water quality improvement, wetlands provide a rich suite of ecosystem services, including habitat and biodiversity support, carbon storage, and flood abatement (Costanza et al., 2014; de Groot et al., 2012; Zedler, 2003; Zedler & Kercher, 2005). However, wetlands, like all ecosystems, can also produce ecosystem disservices. This includes undesired outcomes like emission of the greenhouse gases methane and N_2O and support of invasive species like *Phragmites*, *Phalaris*, and others. The provisioning of a specific service can be limited by trade-offs with other services or can be enhanced by synergies (Jessop et al., 2015; Rodríguez et al., 2006). For example, a wetland that is a monoculture of the invasive *Phragmites* may not support biodiversity but is effective at carbon storage and nutrient removal (Windham, 2001). At times, management decisions that enhance nutrient removal function may constrain a wetland's ability to provide other services due to inherent trade-offs (Jessop et al., 2015).

The H2Ohio Monitoring Program acknowledges complementary, external efforts could be developed to assess co-benefits of each Project including habitat and biodiversity support. Ultimately, efforts to mechanistically understand nutrient removal function in diverse Projects in concert with assessing co-benefits and trade-offs with other ecosystem services can inform future wetland design and management. *The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program aims to specifically assess the nutrient removal ecosystem services provided by ODNR-implemented H2Ohio Wetland Projects.*

3.7 Evidence for Wetland Nutrient Removal and Knowledge Gaps

Evidence is strong that wetlands can effectively retain and remove nutrients (Johnston, 1991; Vymazal, 2007). However, few, if any, past efforts have used a standardized approach to assess ecosystem-scale nutrient budgets and within-ecosystem biogeochemical processes in multiple types of wetlands over ecologically relevant time scales. Many individual site-based studies demonstrate the potential for wetland ecosystems to remove N and/or P (Cheng & Basu, 2017). Detailed nutrient cycling studies have been completed in single and highly engineered treatment wetland systems, but these results are published from the framework of individual systems and are often published only in grey literature rather than peer-reviewed publications (Kovacic et al., 2000). Substantial knowledge has been generated as to the functioning of restored ecosystems in regionally important, but biogeochemically unique wetland systems. For example, most notably there have been wetlands aimed at mitigating excess P loads to the Everglades, Florida as part of the Comprehensive Everglades Restoration Plan (South Florida Water Management District, 2018). Among single-site studies, few have simultaneously determined net ecosystem nutrient budgets along with a mechanistic understanding of the within-wetland processes. *The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program fills a gap in wetland science and policy by directly assessing biogeochemical functions in multiple wetlands of contrasting structure, history, and management at sub-seasonal temporal resolution over multiple years using standardized protocols within a unified framework.*

Most traditional wetland monitoring programs designed to assess ecosystem status or health across large numbers of wetlands are not designed to assess the biogeochemistry and/or nutrient cycling functions of wetland ecosystems directly over relevant (i.e., long-term) time scales. The techniques used by many federal and state wetland monitoring and assessment programs, including the Ohio Rapid Assessment Method (Mack, 2001), are rooted in the hydrogeomorphic classification system originally developed in 1993 (Brinson, 1993) and adapted to serve as an assessment of wetland functional capacity in 1995 (Smith et al., 1995). The ongoing Great Lakes Coastal Wetlands Monitoring Program has monitored over 1000 Great Lakes coastal wetlands every 5 years since 2011, but the primary focus of that effort is to assess overall ecosystem health through biotic and abiotic structural metrics, and not to quantify or assess wetland biogeochemical function such as nutrient retention (Uzarski et al., 2017).

Functional assessments that rely on structural measures and observations are built on the assumption that wetlands with certain biotic quality and hydrogeomorphic features according to traditional classification systems effectively remove nutrients (Hilderbrand et al., 2005). This has

been referred to as the “Field of Dreams” hypothesis in the ecosystem restoration literature (Hilderbrand et al., 2005; Palmer et al., 1997). *The word “function” can be broadly used to describe many wetland features, but here the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program uses the word “function” to refer to biogeochemical processes and rates affecting water quality; specifically, nutrient retention and/or removal processes.*

While characterizing the hydrology, geomorphology, and dominant plant communities is crucial for understanding nutrient removal patterns, an emerging and increasing body of research demonstrates that these structural features do not alone demonstrate nutrient removal effectiveness or magnitude (Sudduth et al., 2011). Only direct measures of nutrient cycling processes, through measuring soil-scale process rates and/or ecosystem-scale nutrient mass balance budgets, conclusively demonstrate wetland nutrient function. These direct measures are necessary to assess the current and future role that wetland types may play toward limiting watershed-scale nutrient loads. Without direct measures of nutrients, efforts to strategically implement wetlands as part of a portfolio of Best Management Practices to mitigate nutrient loading and subsequent eutrophication will remain under-informed.

Besides the aforementioned historical focus on structure rather than direct measure of function, the general lack of monitoring over sufficient time scales to assess restoration success is a commonly cited deficiency in wetland restoration programs (National Research Council, 2001). Even among scientific ecological research efforts, long-term monitoring of wetland ecosystems is rare. Although coastal wetland ecosystems have been intensively studied in long-term monitoring programs at places like the National Science Foundation (NSF) funded Plum Island (MA), Virginia Coastal Reserve, Georgia Coastal Ecosystems, and Florida Coastal Ecosystems Long-Term Ecological Research (LTER) programs, consistent biogeochemical monitoring of *multiple inland restored* wetland ecosystems is not robustly represented in any of the NSF funded LTER sites or the National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON). *The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program advocates for multi-year monitoring of H2Ohio Wetland Projects post-completion using a tiered approach to comprehensively and directly assess nutrient removal through mass balance budgeting in select intensively monitored Projects, along with more extensive assessment of soil and water indices of biogeochemical function.*

4 Monitoring Goals: Nutrient Function Measurements and Indices

The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program combines direct measures and indices of nutrient retention, removal, and process rates to assess the nutrient reduction functions of H2Ohio Wetland Projects. Projects are extraordinarily variable, and no single assessment approach can be used across all Projects. Program researchers are developing a toolkit for achieving data synthesis goals at appropriate scales across diverse systems.

Nutrient load reduction estimates based on direct monitoring of nutrient inputs and outputs for each wetland provide the most useful, policy-relevant information to evaluate the effectiveness of individual Wetland Projects. Annual load reduction values allow the Monitoring Program to track changes in the effectiveness of Wetland Projects over time, compare Projects to one another, and compare wetland restoration approaches to other best management practices. Intensive sampling can also reveal mechanisms underlying nutrient loads and can inform future wetland design and management. However, the high-resolution sampling and detailed experimentation necessary to produce complete nutrient budgets and comprehensive mechanistic understanding are not economically feasible to implement across all Projects. Thus, the Program is using a tiered sampling approach to develop comprehensive nutrient budgets and mechanistic understanding in a representative subset of intensively monitored Focal Projects and develop evidence-based indices to assess nutrient removal in the remainder of less intensively monitored Non-focal Projects. *This chapter of the Monitoring Framework describes the Program's tiered monitoring approach, including the difference between "measuring a wetland's vital signs" and intensive nutrient budgeting, along with consideration of temporal and spatial scales.*

4.1 Tiered Monitoring Approach

Each year, Projects in the Wetland Monitoring Program are designated in one of three tiers: 1) intensively monitored *Focal Projects*, 2) routinely sampled *Non-focal Projects* ("Tier 1 Non-focal"), and 3) intermittently sampled Projects ("Tier 2 Non-focal"). The aim of intensively monitored Focal Projects is to produce full-scale nutrient budgets, as well as mechanistic information about the processes occurring within the wetland, in order to inform our understanding of wetland nutrient biogeochemistry and enable more efficient and effective evaluation of the larger number of Non-focal Projects. The number of Projects monitored in each of these three categories is likely to change from year to year subject to Monitoring Program resources and capacity.

Focal Projects are designated for intensive monitoring including: a sensor network designed to monitor all major hydrologic flows, frequent surface water sampling, and higher resolution soil sampling and characterization. Data collected in Focal Projects present the rare opportunity to conduct simultaneous whole-ecosystem mass balance nutrient budgeting and soil-scale mechanistic process studies, information which can also be used to validate lower cost and less labor-intensive indices used as proxies for whole-wetland nutrient function.

Focal Projects are carefully selected to represent major “types” of wetland creation, restoration and enhancements. These Projects are chosen to yield findings and understandings that can be applied most efficiently and effectively to the evaluation of the largest number of H2Ohio Wetland Projects. Focal Projects are also selected with consideration of monitoring logistics, capacity, visibility, and partner involvement, with the objective of investing heavily in monitoring Focal Projects with a high potential for feasibly completing nutrient budgets. The feasibility of complete nutrient budget accounting is influenced by many factors including the system’s hydrologic processes and features, accessibility, and partner collaboration. The number of Focal Projects designated each year will likely vary based on specific monitoring goals, data collection objectives, staffing capacity, and resource availability, but may typically range from 5–10 Projects. Focal Projects are often designated for multiple years in a row to ensure sufficient data collection to develop 3-D hydrodynamic and other models to fully estimate water and nutrient budgets for the Project sites over time. Even when a Focal Project is taken off the “Focal” list, the models and understanding that have been developed for that Focal Project allow for tracking changes over time (e.g., annual estimated nutrient load reduction to be estimated from less frequent and intensive direct sampling).

Non-focal Projects are designated for less intensive monitoring than Focal Projects including deploying a more limited set of sensors to detect water level fluctuations, less frequent surface water sampling, and soil sampling for soil nutrient status in representative patches at least once after restoration construction is complete. Because the quantity of ODNR-implemented Wetland Projects continues to grow, an additional Tier, Tier 2 Non-focal Projects (approved at the 2024 All-Hands Workshop), consists of intermittently sampled Projects, in which on-the-ground sampling is conducted less frequently than Tier 1 Non-focal Projects. In Tier 1 Non-focal Projects, researchers aim to assess nutrient removal function with evidence-based indicators of nutrient removal capacity and model-based estimates of nutrient removal. In Tier 2 Non-focal Projects, researchers aim to estimate nutrient removal function based on structural and spatial data provided by *Project partners*, infrequent sampling, and lessons learned from the directly sampled Focal and Tier 1 Non-focal Projects.

4.2 Measuring a Wetland’s Vital Signs: Nutrient Retention and Removal Indicators Measured in All Sampled Projects

Across all monitored Wetland Projects, researchers measure water levels, surface water nutrient concentrations, and basic soil nutrients. In Non-focal Projects, where samples are taken less frequently than in Focal Projects, snapshot measurements are like taking a wetland’s “vital signs.” In the short term, these vital signs may not comprehensively quantify net annual nutrient retention, but they can indicate nutrient status, function, and removal potential. Over the longer term, researchers can validate the indicator measurements using the findings generated by Focal Project analyses to produce useful estimates of wetland function to achieve the goals of the Monitoring Program within the limits of available resources. Generally, data can be collected repeatedly to generate a long-term record of nutrient status which can inform broader models and assumptions about the collective influence of wetlands on nutrient management strategies.

4.2.1 *Routine Water Level Monitoring*

No assessment of wetland nutrient function is complete without basic knowledge of hydrologic conditions. Knowing when, where, and how an ecosystem is hydrologically connected to its landscape is critical to assessing its impacts on nutrient loads. Additionally, documenting when, where, and how water moves through or is stored in a wetland indicates the physicochemical and ecological conditions shaping biogeochemical processes and supports estimation of nutrient storage in surface waters. The Monitoring Program will surveil hydrology in all sampled Projects using a combination of repeated manual water depth measures at fixed locations and automated high temporal resolution monitoring using logging water level sensors.

Each monitored Project will contain at least one fixed location where water depths are routinely measured at a staff gauge or other permanent marker. Additionally, researchers will measure water depths whenever surface water samples and/or inundated soil samples are collected at the location of sampling. As budget resources allow, automated logging water level sensors will be deployed in each monitored Project. See *Monitoring Water Quality and Quantity: Water Sampling and Sensor Systems* for additional details on monitoring water level.

Interpreting routinely monitored water level data

When paired with adequate topographic data, water levels monitored at a single location can be used to estimate the depth and spatial extent of inundation, as well as the volume of water stored, throughout a wetland ecosystem. In some systems, water levels can indicate when wetland ecosystems are connected to one another (i.e., in the case of pools which alternate between connected and isolated based on water levels) and to their landscape (i.e., in floodplains, outflows with defined spill points set by water level controls and engineered structures). Using rating curve calculations, continuously monitored water levels within flowing channels support estimates of discharge which can then be paired with nutrient concentration data to estimate nutrient loads at key inflows and outflows.

4.2.2 *Routine Surface Water Nutrient Monitoring*

Within most monitored Projects, surface water locations, including major intermittent and perennial flows and standing water bodies, will be sampled for surface water nutrient concentrations. Sampling will include measuring concentrations of total nitrogen, total phosphorus, nitrate, soluble reactive phosphorus, ammonium, and, when logistically feasible, total suspended solids and other major cations and anions. The goal is to collect surface water in each major season (3–4 times per year) at every Non-Focal Tier 1 Project where standing water is deep enough to be sampled (> ~ 5 cm) during ambient or baseflow conditions, and in response to at least two hydrologic events. Surface water sampling is completed at a higher frequency at Focal Projects.

Interpreting routine surface water nutrient concentration data

When assessing surface water nutrient concentrations, interpretation will be mindful of the “snapshot” nature of infrequent surface water nutrient concentration measurements and informed by knowledge from the literature, expert experience, and intensively monitored Focal Projects about the temporal heterogeneity in nutrient conditions that is not being directly observed in Non-focal Projects.

Preliminary surface water data interpretation can allow for identification of extreme values that might be cause for concern or for increased sampling effort. Measures of relatively high nutrient concentrations, particularly in ecosystem effluent, in comparison to nearby water bodies and the ecosystem’s inflow, can indicate that a Project may be acting as a nutrient source. A Project illustrating “red flag” indicator of nutrient release in the form of high surface water concentrations in outflows relative to inflows may prompt an update of the Project Specific Monitoring Plan to follow up with more sampling. Specific concentrations indicating “red flags” will be context-specific and, in part, based on prior data collected at a given Project site and other similar Project sites, but also shaped by the literature and expert knowledge of typical nutrient conditions in wetland ecosystems that are not receiving high nutrient loads.

In isolated, depressional systems, nutrient concentrations in excess of what is typically observed in rainfall may indicate internal nutrient release but may not be a concern if the isolated system is not discharging to downstream environments via surface or groundwater flow paths. In flow-through systems, nutrient concentrations can provide a snapshot of nutrient removal function during ambient conditions. Along flow paths, researchers aim to compare whether concentrations are greater or lower at outflow(s) than inflow(s). Substantially greater concentrations at an ecosystem outflow could indicate internal nutrient release, while lower concentrations at outflow indicate potential nutrient sequestration, at least under the conditions that are represented by the sampling event. When water level monitoring and/or structural information (i.e., storage volumes) is sufficient to estimate discharge rates, nutrient loads can be estimated.

4.2.3 Soil Characterization and Nutrient Status

Many of the critical nutrient removal (and release) processes occurring in wetlands are mediated by soils. Basic soil measurements can indicate the total quantity of nutrients stored in soils, the amount of bioavailable and easily mobilized inorganic nutrients, and the capacity of soils to sorb phosphate. Moisture content, pH, and electrical conductivity indicate general soil conditions. Measures of total carbon, total inorganic carbon, total organic carbon, total phosphorus, and total nitrogen indicate the total quantity of nutrients stored in sampled soils. Many soil measurements integrate processes occurring over long-time scales and can contain signals of past land use through the accumulation of legacy nutrients. *Thus, sampling for a common suite of straightforward, but informative soil parameters occur at least once every two years in as many H2Ohio Wetland Projects as is feasible for standard and uniform metrics that are robust to the diversity of restoration types and structures.*

Interpreting soil nutrient status data

Water-extractable nutrient concentrations indicate the amount of phosphate (PO_4^{3-}), nitrate, and ammonium in soils that can be easily mobilized and released and are considered hydrologically mobile, meaning it is likely they can be removed from the soil by rain and surface water (Darrouzet-Nardi & Weintraub, 2014; Roswall et al., 2021). The Mehlich-3 extraction uses a more reactive acidic extraction solution than water to extract the P that is sorbed to metal oxide minerals in soils and is intended to mimic the action of plant roots on soils and the ability of plant roots to extract nutrients. Although operationally defined, the Mehlich-3 extraction is a widely accepted and broadly used soil test for P bioavailability. By comparing the amount of P extracted by the Mehlich-3 reagent to the amount of sorptive iron and aluminum that are simultaneously extracted, researchers can assess the capacity of the soil to sorb more P and, conversely, the potential for the soil to release P (Nair et al., 2011, 2015). The molar ratio of P to sorptive metals ($\text{P}/(\text{Fe}+\text{Al})$) is the Phosphorus Saturation Ratio (PSR). Research indicates that a PSR of 0.1 $\text{P}/(\text{Fe}+\text{Al})$ is a critical threshold for many soils at which P sorption sites are saturated (Dari et al., 2018; Nair et al., 2015).

In calculating the Soil Phosphorus Storage Capacity (SPSC), researchers assess the capacity of the soil to sorb or release PO_4^{3-} by comparing the soil's PSR to the literature-based threshold PSR. Soils with a negative SPSC are likely to release PO_4^{3-} , while positive values indicate the soil's capacity to sorb more PO_4^{3-} (Nair et al., 2011; VanZomerem & Berkowitz, 2020). SPSC values near zero indicate that the soil will neither retain nor release PO_4^{3-} . Monitoring Program researchers aim to use SPSC as an early indicator of soil nutrient storage and release potential. As more data is collected, comprehensive nutrient retention and release monitoring in restored wetlands can validate these SPSC-based predictions of ecosystem nutrient function. The Program will refine the use of the SPSC indicator as needed.

4.3 Intensive Monitoring: Nutrient Budget Measurements and Mechanistic Understanding in Select Focal Projects

Nutrient load reductions in units of mass per area per time are the most policy-relevant, directly applicable metric of wetland nutrient removal. They allow assessment of the contribution of a specific practice to watershed-scale nutrient load mitigation goals, including the IJC's target of reducing P loading to the Western Basin of Lake Erie by 40% to mitigate recurring HABs (International Joint Commission, 2014). Annual nutrient load reduction estimates also can be used to track the trajectory of a wetland system through time, compare across wetland systems of different kinds, and compare wetlands to other best management practices aimed at nutrient pollution mitigation, including through cost-benefit analyses. The Monitoring Program aims to estimate nutrient load reductions at all Focal Projects. Additionally, mechanistic investigation and understanding at select Focal Projects allows for scaling up of certain nutrient removal processes across space and time and can support inferences at less-frequently monitored Projects.

To use the mass balance method to calculate an ecosystem's nutrient budget, researchers essentially treat an ecosystem like a bank account by calculating the total amount (or load) of a material (like water, nitrogen, or phosphorus) entering an ecosystem and the total amount leaving an ecosystem over a given period of time, often a year. If the total amount of nutrients leaving the system is less than the total that have entered, then the ecosystem is a sink for that nutrient. If more nutrients leave than enter, the system is a source of that nutrient.

In aquatic ecosystems with constrained inflows and outflows, budgets are often calculated by measuring the volume of water entering and leaving over time, and the amount of nutrients being carried by that water as a concentration. To calculate the total mass of a nutrient entering or leaving over a given time, or the nutrient load, the concentration of a nutrient in mass per volume is multiplied by the volume entering or leaving over a period of time. In practice, it is rarely possible to directly measure nutrient loads at all times and at all ecosystem entries and exits. Monitoring to complete nutrient budgets at a high-confidence, high-resolution level can be complex, costly and data-intensive, particularly in wetlands that do not have easily monitorable, constrained, unidirectional inflows and outflows.

Nutrient concentrations must be measured at sufficient temporal scales and frequency to capture "hot moments," including rain and thaw events, and other temporally distributed seasonal variability in wetland ecosystems. Adequate water sampling can be labor-intensive but produces a complete accounting for an accurate mass balance assessment of nutrient fluxes and the opportunity to explore temporal patterns in nutrient loads. Temporal patterns are especially important because wetlands that are able to absorb nutrient inputs and delay the discharge of nutrients into water bodies during critical periods may be nearly as effective as wetlands that permanently sequester nutrients, a feature which can inform policy and management decisions. *The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program addresses these challenges with whole-ecosystem nutrient mass balance assessments in select, intensively monitored Focal Projects to demonstrate nutrient removal function.*

The Monitoring Program prioritizes monitoring for the following major fluxes: surface water loads, groundwater loads, fluxes between soils and surface water, and sediment deposition and accumulation rates. The major storage pools estimated are the nutrients stored in soils and in plant biomass (Figure 9). Specific monitoring approaches and sampling designs are developed for each Focal Project based on its structure and described in that Project's *Project Specific Monitoring Plan*. For each of the major nutrient budget pools and fluxes, some may be de-emphasized or not estimated at all, given the specific nature of each wetland, feasibility, resources, and capacity. For example, surface water load fluxes might not be characterized in systems without constrained inflow and outflow streams. In these "isolated" wetlands, more effort may be allocated towards quantifying exchange with groundwater and nutrient retention relative to nutrient export estimated prior to wetland construction.

Nutrient budget components that are not explicitly mentioned in this Monitoring Framework are presumed to be minor in comparison to major inflow and outflow loads. Potentially relevant but minor nutrient fluxes, such as loads from atmospheric deposition and waterfowl defecation, may be estimated from published literature sources or assumed to be negligible, unless there is strong evidence that warrants use of Monitoring Program resources to estimate them through direct empirical measurements. The Program aims to assess the adequacy of our conceptual nutrient budget models considering empirical data and emerging knowledge in relevant literature during composition of the *Annual Report* and during the *All-Hands Workshop*, and adjust sampling as needed.

Figure 9. Major nutrient (N & P) pools and fluxes that the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program aims to estimate toward ecosystem-level nutrient budgets.

4.3.1 Surface Water Input and Output Loads

To measure nutrient loads into and out of systems carried by surface water, the Program combines 1) high-resolution, sensor-supported hydrologic monitoring to calculate discharge volumes at key inflow and outflow points with 2) discrete surface water sampling at high temporal resolution during ambient conditions and hydrologic events for concentrations of major nutrients, including dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP), ammonia (NH_4^+), nitrate (NO_3^-), total nitrogen (TN), and total phosphorus (TP). In systems where surface water connections are not constrained in discrete flow paths like floodplains, riparian wetlands, and wetlands receiving diffuse surface water runoff, the Monitoring Program designs hydrologic modeling using water level sensors and other appropriate tools to quantify hydrologic flows into and out of the wetland system, combined with measurements of nutrient concentrations. Where possible, the Program deploys automated turbidity sensors and develops project site-specific relationships between discrete grab-sample based measurements of total P and other water quality parameters with the automated turbidity sensor measurements to use turbidity as a proxy for total P concentrations.

Ambient condition (i.e., baseflow) sampling of adequate temporal resolution, dictated by the nature of the system, is supported by manual grab-sampling. Event-based sampling is supported by automated water samplers (e.g., ISCOs) where resources are available. After sufficient structural, meteorological, and hydrologic data have been gathered in intensively monitored Focal Projects, the Monitoring Program uses 3-D hydrodynamic models (Hydrogeosphere) built for each Project to synthesize hydrologic data and calculate comprehensive hydrologic and nutrient fluxes into and out of the Project site and its components.

4.3.2 Groundwater Load Fluxes

Surface water and groundwater are connected in most landscapes and understanding groundwater exchange is necessary to fully assess nutrient retention (Winter, 1999). However, assessing groundwater discharge and recharge and associated subsurface nutrient load fluxes is notoriously challenging. Where resources allow, the Monitoring Program combines soil geophysical mapping with groundwater monitoring and sampling wells to characterize hydrogeologic settings and measure water levels (hydraulic heads) and nutrient concentrations in groundwater. Data provide detailed information about topography, geology (e.g., permeability of soil and surface-water beds) and groundwater movement (water-table configuration and flow direction with respect to wetland setting). Moreover, the 3-D models built for Focal Projects integrate both surface-water and groundwater domains, allowing spatially-explicit quantification of water and nutrient exchanges between the subsurface and wetlands.

4.3.3 Hydrodynamic Modeling

When sufficient data has been collected in Focal Projects, the Program will develop fully integrated numerical models capable of simulating surface–subsurface flow and transport processes in a 3-D framework to assist wetland water budget and nutrient removal efficiency calculations (Aquanty, 2018; Liu et al., 2016). The 3-D hydrologic models simulate water movement and nutrient transport in the interacting surface–subsurface systems in a physically based manner that relies on coupled differential equations (Figure 10). The models are driven by climate data (precipitation, temperature, evaporation, etc.) and calibrated/validated against directly measured water levels (groundwater and surface water levels), flows, and/or chemistry (e.g., nutrient concentration).

Figure 10. Hydrologic Modeling: Schematic flowchart of key hydrologic processes in a depressional wetland hydrologic model (adapted from Liu & Schwartz, 2011).

4.3.4 Soil Storage Pool

To estimate bulk storage of available nutrients and total nutrient mass in soils, the Monitoring Program will aim to measure soil bulk density as well as a suite of standard soil analyses described above (water-extractable nutrients, Mehlich-3 extractions, and total N and P). Stratified discrete soil sampling aims to estimate soil nutrient storage in known or assumed patch areas. Researchers aim to combine discrete point measurements of soil nutrient content with soil mapping supported by geophysical techniques to estimate per-area rates of soil nutrient storage.

4.3.5 Soil-Surface Water Fluxes

Substantial nutrient retention and removal occurs via soil processes, including PO_4^{3-} sorption, total P accumulation and burial, and removal of inorganic N by transformation to N gases via denitrification (Reddy & DeLaune, 2008). Using various techniques, these soil fluxes can be directly measured or indicated by proxy measurements. In wetlands with complex hydrologic structures, such as floodplain wetlands, coastal wetlands, and primarily groundwater-fed wetlands, the only and/or best option for assessing nutrient removal is to measure flux and storage pools in isolated soil system components that can be compared and synthesized for whole-ecosystem mass balance accounting.

To estimate soil-water nutrient fluxes at select Focal Project locations, the Monitoring Program performs incubations that are standard in the field of benthic biogeochemistry and rely on collecting intact sediment cores that preserve sediment-water interface structure and redox gradients (Boedecker et al., 2020; McCarthy et al., 2015). In flooded environments, sediment-surface water nutrient fluxes and *in situ* denitrification and other process rates can be measured through carefully designed lab incubation experiments, where sediment cores are collected and incubated in a flow-through system under environmentally relevant conditions. Flux rates of N₂ gas, inorganic nutrients, organic nutrients, and other major ions are calculated by measuring concentrations in influent and effluent water passing through each incubated core. The addition of new N via net N fixation (more N₂ consumption than is balanced by loss through denitrification) can be detected in the same incubations. When these single-point flux rate measurements are appropriately replicated, scaled to represent biogeochemical dominant ecosystem patches, and placed within the context of other nutrient removal and retention processes, they can provide an invaluable measure of wetland nutrient biogeochemical fluxes at ecosystem scales.

To directly measure nutrient fluxes at the soil surface in select Focal Project locations, the Monitoring Program deploys stacked resin bags at the soil surface (McMillan & Noe, 2017; Noe et al., 2013, 2019). This method is particularly useful for detecting nutrient loads and fluxes in systems where monitoring inflowing inorganic nutrient loads through surface water sampling is infeasible (e.g., some floodplain, coastal, and depressional wetlands). Each stacked resin bag is constructed such that resin bags on the bottom, in contact with the soil, integrate inorganic nutrient fluxes from sediments into surface waters, and resin bags in the top of the sampler, in contact with surface waters, integrate inorganic nutrient fluxes from surface waters into the sediment. When deployed at sufficient spatial extent (i.e., covering enough wetland area) and resolution (i.e., enough points distributed within the area), these single-point inorganic flux rates can be scaled up to estimate whole-ecosystem rates of inorganic nutrient flux into and out of wetland soils and sediments (Noe et al., 2019).

4.3.6 *Sediment Deposition and Accumulation*

In wetlands receiving substantial sediment loads, particularly floodplain wetlands, a major P retention mechanism is the deposition, accrual, and burial of P-laden particles. In systems where substantial P retention may occur via the deposition and burial of sediments (e.g., floodplain and coastal wetlands), and when resources and conditions allow, the Monitoring Program uses artificial horizon markers (e.g., feldspar clay) to measure sedimentation rates (Hupp & Bazemore, 1993). Where sediment is accrued above sedimentation markers deployed at known times, researchers aim to collect cores and measure nutrient concentration in accumulated material, in order to permit direct measurement of nutrient accumulation rates through sediment deposition (Noe et al., 2019).

4.3.7 *Vegetation Storage Pool*

When possible, to complete estimates of nutrient fluxes and storage, particularly in non-flow-through wetlands, researchers combine plant tissue nutrient analyses with estimates of plant biomass and coverage to estimate plant nutrient uptake and storage. The Monitoring Program uses a combination of on-the-ground plant community composition surveys, autonomously collected aerial imagery (drones) and other maps, and plant tissue nutrient analysis to estimate plant nutrient storage pool quantities.

4.4 Temporal and Spatial Scales and Extents

The restoration, creation, or enhancement approaches being used across individual H2Ohio Projects vary widely, but what all Projects have in common is that they are being implemented at the scale of an ecosystem. Thus, the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program prioritizes observations at temporal and spatial scales that are appropriate for ecosystem-level assessment of nutrient biogeochemistry.

4.4.1 *A Matter of Time: Long-term Monitoring, Seasonal and Event Sampling*

Ecological systems change over time, and only long-term data can comprehensively reveal function and trajectory (Knapp et al., 2012; Wolkovich et al., 2014). To accurately assess any ecological system, long-term monitoring that both captures variability at sufficient temporal resolution and continues for a sufficient extent of time to detect long-term patterns is necessary. Some ecosystem processes, such as development of soil properties that are conducive to water quality improvement (e.g., organic matter content), take decades to achieve levels similar to undisturbed reference wetlands (Ballantine & Schneider, 2009). Year-to-year and season-to-season variability and anomalous events can obscure long-term trends if a system is not monitored at the appropriate frequency and over a sufficient period of time (Cusser et al., 2020; Gooseff, 2017; White, 2019). Ecological variability has become even more pronounced due to climate change, with increasing variability of weather conditions.

Annual net nutrient budgets are often the most policy-relevant metrics of ecosystem function. The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program advocates for at least ten years of sustained monitoring of annual functional measurements derived from sufficiently resolved data that incorporate seasonal variability and “hot moments.” To calculate accurate annual measures, Program researchers determine the temporal frequency of fine-scale measurements (e.g., surface water nutrient concentrations) according to the temporal variation of a given parameter based on existing knowledge (e.g., the Tributary Loading Program run by the National Center for Water Quality Research) and expert knowledge from Program researchers. This same expert knowledge can be used to characterize uncertainty around annual load estimates based on temporal sampling frequency.

Many biogeochemical processes occur at higher rates during “hot moments,” in which relatively short events contribute unduly to the cumulative function of an ecosystem (Bernhardt et al., 2017; McClain et al., 2003). For example, over the course of an entire year, the vast majority of nutrient loads can be delivered to and/or from an ecosystem during relatively few high discharge events (Zhu et al., 2012). In wetlands, other “hot moment” events include re-flooding increasing stream discharge in floodplain wetlands, re-wetting in drained and dried isolated and depression ponds, lowering water level control structures to release water from wetland hydrologic units, and wind-driven seiches that cause extreme water level fluctuations in ecosystems along the coast of the western basin of Lake Erie (Gu et al., 2012). *The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program aims to explicitly target event-based sampling by characterizing the nature of meaningful events in individual Projects based on their hydrologic structure.*

The timing of monitoring across seasons and within years is also of particular relevance to mitigating eutrophication and HABs, as the seasonal timing of nutrient loading into vulnerable ecosystems has important implications for whether or not nutrients will significantly contribute to algal growth (Paerl et al., 2011). In particular, spring runoff (i.e., March 1 – July 30) entering Lake Erie via the Maumee River contributes to the nutrient loads that fuel late summer HABs (Stumpf et al., 2012). Therefore, the ability of wetlands to sequester nutrients during the critical spring months may be more important in reducing HABs than their net annual nutrient sequestration. *The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program aims to account for seasonal dynamics in its monitoring plans and measurements.*

4.4.2 Spaced Out: Ecosystem, Zone, and Point Spatial Scales

Measurements within ecosystems contribute to both whole-ecosystem assessment and knowledge of within-ecosystem nutrient storage and biogeochemical processes (Figure 11). Wetlands are spatially heterogeneous (Batzer & Sharitz, 2006; Mitsch & Gosselink, 2015). Spatial variability is shaped by variation in hydroperiod associated with topographic structure, leading to characteristic wetland plant assemblages and soil characteristics (Batzer & Sharitz, 2006; Casanova & Brock, 2000). Just as adequate temporal resolution must be identified, measurements must be taken at sufficient spatial resolution, capturing dominant, representative areas as well as disproportionally influential locations (“hot spots”) to accurately reflect the system as a whole (Bernhardt et al., 2017; McClain et al., 2003).

Available topographic, hydrologic, soil, and plant data are used by researchers to delineate zones within each Project, guide stratified sampling, and scale up measurements to estimate whole-ecosystem nutrient function. Initially, available aerial imagery, design maps, publicly available soil data, and Project visits are used to manually delineate zones. Zone boundaries may change as understanding of each Project is enhanced through data collection, and as each Project itself changes due to erosion, plant community development, structural interventions by managers, etc. The delineation and use of zones to stratify point sampling can assist researchers in generating sample locations. If it is apparent that other obvious gradients and/or putative “hot spots” (e.g., where two distinct flow paths meet, as in a groundwater seepage location or a tributary entry point) are not represented, additional points can be identified to ensure adequate sampling.

As of June 2024, individual Project areas range from 0.5 to 995 acres. The size of zones delineated within each ecosystem generally relates to Project size (in terms of total area), such that larger Projects inevitably contain zones of larger size. Spatial areas that discrete sampling points represent also vary depending on the nature of the measurement. For example, a soil sample taken at a discrete point may represent conditions in a more constrained spatial area than a water sample taken at a discrete point (although a soil sample integrates information over a longer time period than a water sample at a given time).

Figure 11. Illustration of the spatial scale considered in assessment of H2Ohio Wetland Projects. Projects are nested within *watersheds*, and are generally considered at ecosystem, zone, and point scales. Nutrient budgeting ecosystem units can be assessed by studying delineated *zones* (>100 m²) within systems, as defined by hydrogeomorphic features, dominant vegetative communities, and soil characteristics. Soils, water quality, and other parameters are monitored by sampling at discrete *points* within each zone.

4.4.3 Watershed Scale Contextualization

Ultimately, the success of the broader H2Ohio initiative will be determined by how individual Wetland Projects in addition to other interventions (e.g., on-field best management practices) influence nutrient loads at watershed and regional scales. As of June 2024, assessing the role of H2Ohio Wetland Projects within the broader landscape and from a watershed context is outside of the scope of the current Monitoring Program, but researchers aim to produce ecosystem-level, annual-time scale information that could be used in future efforts to compare the costs and benefits of various Wetland Project approaches with other interventions, as well as to inform watershed-scale modeling to assess the current and potential role of restored and constructed wetlands at watershed scales.

5 Project-Specific Monitoring

Although the Wetland Monitoring Program has general guidelines and minimum data collection requirements for monitoring all Projects (within designations as Focal, Tier 1 Non-focal, or Tier 2 Non-focal), each individual Project still requires unique sampling designs due to the diversity in size, structure, and restoration approaches across the H2Ohio Wetland Projects implemented by the Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR). *This chapter of the Monitoring Framework describes Project-specific categorization and monitoring approaches, Project-specific monitoring timelines and milestones, and creation of Project-specific monitoring plans.*

5.1 H2Ohio Wetland Projects: Diverse Approaches to a Common Goal

The ODNR-implemented [H2Ohio Wetland Program](#) represents a broad range of approaches and techniques to create, restore and enhance wetland ecosystems. This diversity of Projects provides a unique opportunity to better understand what makes a wetland effective at removing nutrients. The following categories are adapted from [US EPA](#) definitions:

- **Wetland creation** refers to establishing a new wetland ecosystem at a location where a wetland does not currently exist or where a wetland never existed in the history of the location.
- **Wetland restoration** refers to the re-establishment or rehabilitation of some or all features of wetland ecosystem function in a location where a wetland was historically present.
- **Wetland enhancement** refers to any practice that is intended to improve wetland ecosystem structure and/or function without changing the total wetland area, including invasive species removal and implementation of structures to increase habitat heterogeneity.

In practice, there is often considerable overlap and ambiguity as to whether the activities of a particular Wetland Project would best be categorized as creation, restoration, or enhancement. Many H2Ohio Wetland Projects involve restoring wetland hydrology to previous hydric soil conditions through disrupting tile drains and moving soil to generate elevational heterogeneity characteristic of natural wetland ecosystems. Several coastal Projects consist primarily of reconnecting existing diked and disconnected coastal wetlands to their watersheds and to Lake Erie. Others, such as Projects planned for Sandusky Bay and Maumee Bay, involve constructing island-type wetlands in locations that are relatively deep (particularly with high Lake Erie water levels, as deep as 1–2 m). *The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program takes a descriptive, attribute- and hydrologic-based approach to understanding the nature of individual Wetland Project creation, restoration, and enhancement activities while also accounting for historical land use and features, rather than formally categorizing Projects as being entirely creation, restoration, and/or enhancement.*

Project Categorization is likely to be an iterative process, and different groupings may be used for different purposes. As they emerge, wetland categories support the planning and implementation of monitoring by providing a basis for robust distribution of resources and effort (i.e., Focal Project selection). Categorizing Projects also supports development of best practices for monitoring different “types” of wetlands, both for internal Monitoring Program use and as guidance to partners interested in monitoring non-H2Ohio wetlands. Ultimately, categorization schemes can guide synthesis of monitoring data at a Program-wide scale toward informing agency decisions about Wetland Project creation, restoration, enhancement, and management.

5.1.1 Categorizing Wetland Projects: Structural Attributes, Design, and Management Regimes

Synthesizing information generated by the Wetland Monitoring Program to inform agency-level decisions about multiple wetlands requires grouping different “types” of Projects. A variety of classification systems for wetland ecosystems have been used globally (Gerbeaux et al., 2018). Many, even those that incorporate functional attributes related to wetland hydrology and geomorphology, are based on structural wetland features, and may not be adequate to inform and/or predict the nutrient function of newly restored, created, or enhanced ecosystems. *The Monitoring Program aims to adapt and improve upon existing classification schemes and identify key features of Wetland Projects that are predictive of nutrient function, in order to generate results directly relevant to agency and partner information needs.*

Information and Project attributes that contribute to categorization include:

A priori Project information (before collecting field data)

- Geography and location parameters (i.e., County, region, watershed).
- Pre-construction land use—on-site and across surrounding landscape.
- Major structural features—as designed or implemented, and/or pre-existing.
- Assumed general hydrologic function (i.e., flow-through, floodplain, coastal, or isolated).
- Regulatory frameworks, permitting, land and site obligations.
- Management regimes as indicated by ownership (e.g., private vs. public), managers, agency divisions, and management plans.

A posteriori Project information (incorporating field-collected data)

- Actual hydrologic function—hydroperiods, discharge, flow versus stagnation, event types, event frequency, event intensity, and surface and subsurface landscape connection.
- Conversations with and data shared by managers and partners regarding management actions and regimes (e.g., water level control decisions and events).

Thus, as the Monitoring Program gathers information about the structure, design, intent, and other attributes of Wetland Projects, researchers aim to explore a variety of categorization approaches, incorporating both traditional classification schemes as well as novel typologies and data-driven clustering (e.g., classification and regression tree).

5.1.2 Hydrologic Structure Shapes Monitoring Approaches

The general hydrologic structure of a Wetland Project is a prominent feature that contributes to project categorization, shapes monitoring efforts, and frames data analysis. Categorization by hydrologic structure provides a straightforward framework to guide monitoring for ecosystem-scale nutrient budgeting because this structure is directly related to how wetland systems are connected to the landscape (Figure 12). Treating each wetland as a discrete unit with inflows and outflows leads to straightforward nutrient budgeting. However, in reality, Projects are defined by jurisdictional and parcel boundaries, not ecosystem boundaries. In addition, many features of wetland hydrology are challenging to cleanly categorize. Some Projects contain multiple of these wetland hydrologic structures, and some distinct wetland ecosystems may represent features of more than one of these categories. For example, the Oakwoods Nature Preserve Wetland Restoration Projects encompass a floodplain wetland and >40 depressional wetland ponds, which may be intermittently connected when surrounding land floods as a wet meadow.

Figure 12. Diagram illustrating the dominate hydrologic structure categories used to guide characterization, categorization, and monitoring of H2Ohio Wetland Projects; flow-through, coastal, floodplain, and depressional.

A Project’s categorization into one or more hydrologic structures can shape, but does not dictate, monitoring approaches. Some wetlands may contain features that fit into multiple categories, and a “one-size-fits-all” and even a “four-sizes-fit-four” approach is not appropriate. Rather, the hydrologic structure and unique features of each individual Project are used to develop Project-specific monitoring approaches. Assessing wetland nutrient function is generally more straightforward in flow-through wetlands with constrained inflows and outflows but Focal Project monitoring also includes groundwater and atmospheric connections (e.g., nitrogen denitrification and fixation). Estimating wetland nutrient retention is generally more challenging for depressional, floodplain, and coastal wetlands, where assessing the nutrient pools of individual components of the ecosystem is warranted to calculate a whole-ecosystem mass balance.

Flow-through wetlands have a limited number of constrained, unidirectional inflows and outflows that are relatively straightforward to monitor. These unidirectional flows lend themselves well to directly measuring hydrologic discharge and nutrient concentrations, permitting accurate load calculations and thus estimates of whole-ecosystem mass balances. In designing Project Specific Monitoring Plans to assess nutrient removal function in flow-through wetlands, special consideration is given to the temporal frequency and resolution of water sample collection for nutrient concentration measurements to ensure that sufficient data are collected to capture seasonal changes in nutrient concentrations as well as event-driven fluxes.

Non-flow-through wetlands are characterized by hydrology that makes load calculations from surface water concentrations more challenging, if not impossible. In coastal, floodplain, and depressional wetlands, researchers aim to employ a combination of surface water monitoring with soil-scale measurements to estimate nutrient mass balances where feasible.

Coastal wetlands are characterized by a combination of constrained, unidirectional flows (typically inflow from upstream watersheds) and bidirectional connections to a larger body of water (i.e., Lake Erie). The magnitude and directionality of hydrologic inputs and outputs to coastal systems are shaped not only by discharge of inflows, but also by Great Lakes water levels, seiche events, and wetland water level management (Kowalski et al., 2014). Coastal H2Ohio Wetland Projects involve enhancing the connection of diked, disconnected Lake Erie coastal wetlands with stream and river networks carrying high nutrient loads, and many involve direct connection to ditches draining agricultural land. Most coastal Wetland Projects contain multiple diked wetland units that are connected to one another at discrete locations, most of which have water level control structures and/or pumps, permitting some human control over reconnected coastal wetland hydrology.

Floodplain wetlands are adjacent to a larger flowing body of water, in most cases a river. These wetlands are laterally and intermittently connected to a river, stream, ditch, or other flowing system. The magnitude, timing, and spatial extent of intermittent flooding are driven by river discharge dynamics, and thus often storm event-driven and seasonal. Subsurface flows also play important roles in the hydrology and biogeochemistry of floodplain wetlands.

Finally, depressional wetlands are those without persistent, constrained hydrologic inflows or outflows. These wetlands are often categorized as “geographically isolated wetlands” by regulatory frameworks, including those in the state of Ohio such as the Ohio Environmental Protection Agency. Although isolated from surface flow stream networks, these wetlands are still hydrologically connected through the landscape by inflows and outflows that are challenging to directly measure and sample, including through groundwater discharge and recharge and through unconstrained overland surface runoff (Cohen et al., 2016). While they lack overt surface connections, “geographically isolated wetlands” retain water and thus reduce P and N export that occurred prior to wetland construction, and this may represent a primary benefit of this type of wetland feature with respect to P and N load reduction. They may also contribute to landscape nutrient cycling through subsurface and other cryptic connections. The Monitoring Program characterizes subsurface and other hydrologic connections in addition to surface water sampling where feasible in depressional wetlands.

5.2 H2Ohio Wetland Projects: Project-Specific Monitoring Timelines

H2Ohio Wetland Projects have been funded and implemented by the ODNR on a rolling basis since the inception of the H2Ohio Initiative in 2020. As of June 2024, 183 Projects have been funded and construction is complete in 98 of these. The Monitoring Program aims to maintain a portfolio of monitored Projects (~45 Projects as of June 2024) that is feasible to monitor within available resources and capacity in any given year and represents a representative sample of the geography, history, restoration approaches, and other attributes of H2Ohio Wetland Projects. In selecting Projects for monitoring, priority is given to Projects that have been monitored in the past to continue building long-term datasets. Each monitored Project is characterized prior to Routine Monitoring as described in the detailed timeline below.

5.2.1 ODNR H2Ohio Project Selection

Individual H2Ohio Wetland Projects are selected and funded by the ODNR through a combination of competitive, application-based grants and discretionary funds. ODNR's H2Ohio Wetland Program began with a geographic focus on funding natural infrastructure work in the Maumee River Watershed and Western Lake Erie Basin watershed and has since expanded across Ohio. In the Lake Erie watershed, ODNR's H2Ohio Program has operated with a discretionary grant funding model in order to expedite implementation timelines. ODNR works directly with grant awardees in this geography to customize scopes of work, budgets, and timelines to fit the urgent need for water quality improvement. In the Ohio River Basin, H2Ohio has used a more traditional competitive, application-based grant funding model which awards funding after review by a panel of staff from different Divisions at ODNR. Future cycles of ODNR's H2Ohio Program will likely continue to strike a balance between competitive and discretionary grant funding, always with an emphasis on getting the best water quality-centered Projects rapidly implemented.

5.2.2 New Projects: ODNR Notifies Monitoring Program

After an H2Ohio Project is granted funding and a contract is in place, the ODNR informs the Monitoring Program of basic information including the Project name, location, and ODNR Project Manager, and a series of separate but periodically coordinated project-specific timeline milestones begin (Figure 13). The Monitoring Program consists of Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network (LEARN). See [**Program Administration**](#) for details about Program Structure, Personnel, and Reporting. The Monitoring Program Research Coordinator assigns new Projects to Base Crews based on their geographic location and facilitates communication between the Base Crew lead and the Project's ODNR Project manager. The ODNR Project manager then connects the Base Crew lead with the *Project collaborators* (i.e., Project grantees, consultants, designers, land managers) to facilitate information sharing.

Figure 13. Project Specific Milestones for H2Ohio Wetland Projects. ODNR Milestones are indicated in red and are generally overseen by ODNR Core Staff. LEARN Milestones are indicated in blue and generally overseen by LEARN Core Staff. Stages at which information is exchanged from the ODNR to LEARN are indicated in purple.

5.2.3 ODNR Milestone: Design & Engineering

Most Project grantees contract with one or more firms to design the restoration and obtain necessary permits during the Design & Engineering phase. During the Design & Engineering phase, Monitoring Program Base Crews, with support from the Research Coordinator, communicate with partners and consultants, when possible, to maintain awareness of wetland design features relevant to monitoring. When appropriate and possible, the Base Crew researchers may recommend inclusion of structures to facilitate monitoring, as long as the structures would not impede the intent of the wetland restoration activities. For example, in wetlands with constrained inflows and/or outflows, researchers may recommend inclusion of structures (e.g., weirs) that are large enough to contain sensors and have geometries that facilitate efficient and effective flow monitoring for discharge calculations. In wetlands with persistent flooding (e.g., many coastal Projects), researchers may suggest inclusion of structures to launch small boats for sample collection. It is not feasible to standardize a single program workflow for such requests and thus the process is situational and depends on the level of communication between the ODNR Project managers, Project collaborators, and Base Crew researchers.

5.2.4 LEARN Milestone: Limited Pre-Construction Sampling

The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program does not rely on before-and-after comparisons to assess the effect of wetland creation, restoration, or enhancement on the nutrient function of a given Project, in part because of limitations to pre-construction sampling. For many ecosystem and restoration ecologists, the Before-After-Control-Impact (BACI) sampling design is a scientific ideal to rigorously determine the impact of environmental interventions. However, pre-construction monitoring is typically unrealistic and may not provide relevant information. Under realistic H2Ohio Wetland Project circumstances, opportunities to collect adequate pre-restoration data are limited. A single year of “Before” monitoring data does not adequately represent year-to-year variability. Meaningful ecosystem-scale nutrient function assessment requires, at a minimum, three to five years of monitoring with sufficient temporal and spatial frequency. Within the H2Ohio ODNR Program, most Wetland Projects move relatively quickly and begin construction within one to two years of initiation. During this pre-construction phase, information regarding wetland design plans is often insufficient to create pre-construction monitoring approaches, in part because design and engineering is often ongoing until immediately prior to construction beginning. In addition, Projects often entail substantial earth moving and reconstruction of landscapes, making data on soils and structural features prior to restoration marginally comparable to post-construction data, at best. The Program’s nutrient budgeting approach aims to estimate as-built Project nutrient load reduction estimates, which can be used to compare across Projects of various types and with other H2Ohio (e.g., agricultural edge of field) interventions. *The nutrient load accounting approach aligns with the goals of the H2Ohio Initiative at large. Wetland Projects are primarily intended to mitigate excess nutrient loads, and not to restore ecosystems to a defined quality status or pre-disturbance reference condition. Thus, the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program aims to provide empirical evidence that can be used to place the nutrient functions of each Project within the context of broader nutrient load patterns and management strategies.*

The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program is mindful of identifying planned Projects with construction timelines that permit adequate and relevant pre-construction sampling, and only invests resources in such sampling where there is reasonable confidence that the resulting information can substantively enrich understanding in policy- and management-relevant ways. When sufficient information exists prior to active construction, Monitoring Program Base Crews aim to assess the value and relevance of collecting samples and data prior to construction. If relevant, data collection occurs where resources are available. Pre-construction sampling typically consists of limited soil sampling and analysis.

5.2.5 ODNR Milestone: Construction

The kinds and intensity of “construction” activities on each Project vary. Although some Projects entail minimal to no active modifications to the landscape (e.g., in the rare case of land acquisition), most involve some degree of earth moving, structure installation, or plantings. After initial introduction via the Monitoring Program Research Coordinator, the ODNR Project Manager connects the Base Crew lead with the Project grantee and any relevant individual(s) to stay up-to-date on construction progress. Minimal, if any, active data collection occurs during the construction phase, and Monitoring Program researchers communicate with collaborators to understand the progress and process. This information helps researchers sufficiently understand specific modification and construction approaches that may later shape wetland function. This phase may or may not include a Project site visit(s) during construction.

5.2.6 LEARN Milestone: Project Characterization and Preliminary Data to Guide Monitoring

If a new Project has been selected for monitoring, after construction is complete, Monitoring Program researchers compile information about, survey, and preliminarily sample the as-built wetland during the Project Characterization phase. Researchers gather information about the primary wetland features, hydrologic traits, land history, restoration approach, management goals, and field visit logistics. This is the phase in which there is the most active interaction across a ODNR Project managers, collaborators and Monitoring Program researchers.

The objectives of Project Characterization are to:

- Meet and establish relationships with Project site owners, managers, and relevant partners to facilitate site access and obtain information about the intention, design, and ongoing management of the Project.
- Map the dominant hydrologic flow paths and features.
- Document relevant Project site history and landscape context.
- Broadly map soil characteristics, vegetative communities, and geomorphology.
- Characterize hydrologic events (e.g., storms, flooding, water level management) to delineate event-based water sampling.

Developing a sampling scheme for any particular wetland requires an understanding of its basic structure and landscape context. The goal of Project Characterization is to generate enough information to develop a Project Specific Monitoring Plan, which defines the parameters, sampling locations, and sampling intensity and frequency for a specific Project. Project Characterization begins after creation, enhancement, or restoration construction activities are completed so that Project Specific Monitoring Plans accurately reflect the Project's as-built features, which do not always align perfectly with design plans. In addition to information compiled from partners, researchers gather data and maps from publicly available sources including aerial images (e.g., Google Earth), soil data (e.g., [USDA NRCS Web Soil Survey](#)), watershed and drainage data (e.g., USGS Watershed Boundary Dataset, USGS, 2020a), and surrounding land cover data (e.g., National Land Cover Dataset, NLCD, 2016). The duration of Project Characterization varies depending on the timing of construction, the availability of existing data, and the complexity of the Project. In some Projects, Characterization may take up to a year, but in many this phase may be shorter. Additionally, the depth of information collected may depend on the project status (i.e., Focal or Non-Focal).

Project Characterization: Catchment Area Mapping

The rapid, widely available and user-friendly [USGS StreamStats](#) online basin delineation tool is used to rapidly characterize the catchment area and land use drained by wetlands within each Project. Once the necessary elevation data have been collected, wetland catchment areas and boundaries are more precisely and accurately delineated using spatial analysis tools in GIS platforms. Where possible, geospatial data on artificial drainage systems (locations of subsurface tile drains, ditches, control structures, etc.) may also be collected (or obtained from existing documentation) and mapped as part of delineation and Project Characterization activities. All putative major inflows, outflows, and hydrologic features identified using remotely sensed and/or digitally obtained geographic data are verified on the ground during Project Characterization visit and subsequent in-person visits.

Project Characterization: Field Visit

Monitoring Program Base Crews visit each as-built Project at least once after construction is completed. During a Project Characterization visit, researchers locate and photograph landscape features that suggest key inflow and outflow points including piped flows, hydrologic management structures (e.g., water level control, pumps), and uncontrolled perennial and intermittent flows. If apparent, they may sketch and/or use GPS to delineate the edges of patches determined visually from a combination of vegetation, elevational changes, and hydrologic and soil indicators. Across the Project site, researchers note general features including water presence (currently deep, currently shallow, dry but evidence of previous inundation, or dry without evidence of inundation), vegetation amount (none, low, medium, or high density; short, medium, or tall), and general vegetation types (none, submerged, low-lying emergent, tall emergent, terrestrial grasses, terrestrial forbs, shrubs, trees).

Project Characterization: Topography and Bathymetry

The Monitoring Program aims to collect topographic and bathymetric data for every Focal Project, and in as many Non-focal Projects as possible. In most cases, Project partners may provide as-built elevation data from their plans and surveying. When necessary, Monitoring Program personnel can gather topographic and bathymetric data using drone flight-obtained data and/or manual on-the-ground surveying techniques.

5.2.7 LEARN Milestone: Routine Project Specific Monitoring

Routine Monitoring for a given Project begins after sufficient information has been gathered to determine sampling and data collection needs to meet monitoring goals. Routine Monitoring always occurs on the as-built structure and hydrology of a Project. During Routine Monitoring, communication between the Monitoring Program Researchers and Project Collaborators often continues, especially where there is active water level management. Within our adaptive framework, each Project Specific Monitoring Plan is updated annually as new information is gathered, as features of the Project site and its surrounding landscape change, and as available resources to support Monitoring Program sampling fluctuate. The specific locations and quantity of sampling points within a given Project may change, as preliminary data improve our understanding of each ecosystem and as each ecosystem itself changes in response to human interventions and non-human influences (e.g., physical disturbances from extreme weather events). Project Specific Monitoring Plans are developed with the assumption that long-term monitoring (i.e., 10 or more years) will be required to fully assess the trajectory of nutrient removal function in H2Ohio Wetland Projects. See **Designing Project Specific Monitoring Plans** for more details about the framework and sampling parameters that guide Project Specific Monitoring Plans.

5.2.8 LEARN Milestone: Routine Monitoring Data Processing and Reporting

In general, monitoring data is processed and checked by a combination of lab-specific and program-wide data management standards. Program researchers actively and routinely communicate to ensure lessons learned from one year's data collection can be applied the following year. See **Program Administration** for more details about program communication and reporting, and see **Data Management and Quality Control** for details about data processing and releases.

5.3 Designing Project Specific Monitoring Plans

Information gathered during the Project Characterization phase is used to develop a full Project Specific Monitoring Plan which details specific monitoring approaches and sampling designs at individual Focal and Non-focal Projects.

Each Project Specific Monitoring Plan includes:

- Overview of data collection goals for the coming year based on the planned frequency and extent of soil and water sampling and other data collection tasks.
- Basic information about the Project including its name, coordinates, access location(s), and contact information for relevant partners, particularly individuals, to refer to if issues with site access arise, and other logistical information about site visitation and sampling.¹
- Brief Project site history, restoration goals and approaches, management plans, including an overview of the hydrologic structure and management of the as-built wetland.
- List and/or links to existing data, particularly long-term monitoring like relevant nearby USGS streamflow and/or weather sensor stations.
- Data analysis plans and goals, including hypothesized or known major pools and fluxes and how each will be measured using collected data and ultimately used to estimate nutrient budgets and load reductions.
- One or more maps of the Project as needed to illustrate access, hydrology, water and soil sampling locations, sensor locations, and features.
- Surface water and soil sampling plans including names, coordinates, and access details for repeated soil and surface water sampling locations and intended frequency.
- Hydrologic event definitions and event-based sampling guidance and goals.
- Locations at which sensors are to be, or are, deployed.
- Overview of specialty sampling crews plans (i.e., Drone, Geophysics, Vegetation, advanced Sensor Network), where relevant.
- Clear instructions with respect to roles and responsibilities including field crew(s) responsible for on-the-ground sampling and lab(s) responsible for sample analysis.

*The following subsections outline the water, soil, and specialty crew sampling parameters and plans that are included in each Project Specific Monitoring Plan, including some high-level information about sampling each parameter. As a reminder see the Monitoring Framework chapters on **Background: Wetlands and Water Quality** and **Monitoring Goals: Nutrient Function Measurements and Indices** for details on the scientific rationale and monitoring program data collection goals that underly the Project Specific Monitoring Plans.*

¹ Some site access and contact information details are redacted from publicly accessible versions of Project-Specific Monitoring Plans

5.3.1 *List and/or links to existing data*

Project Specific Monitoring Plans often highlight lists and/or links to existing data. This list of data may include data collected by project collaborators before or during construction, data collected by Monitoring Program researchers during the Project Characterization phase.

Researchers can see **[H2Ohio Wetland Projects: Project-Specific Monitoring Timelines](#)** to frame this list of data. Additionally, any external data for planned use toward nutrient load calculations or nutrient indicator assessment can be listed here.

5.3.2 *Data Analysis Plans and Goals*

Each Project Specific Monitoring Plan includes a general diagram of the primary inflows, outflows, pools, and fluxes of nutrients guiding the sampling design. In addition, the Plan includes proposed approach for calculating load reduction. The details and depth of planned data analysis are generally greater in Focal than Non-Focal Projects. Researchers can see **[Intensive Monitoring: Nutrient Budget Measurements and Mechanistic Understanding in Select Focal Projects](#)** to help frame the Focal Project data analysis plans and calculations. Researchers can see **[Measuring a Wetland's Vital Signs: Nutrient Retention and Removal Indicators Measured in All Sampled Projects](#)** to help frame Non-focal Project data analysis plans and calculations.

5.3.3 *Monitoring Water Quality and Quantity: Water Sampling and Sensor Systems*

In general, surface water samples are collected in similar kinds of hydrologic features whether from Focal or Non-focal Projects to measure concentrations of major nutrients, including dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) ammonia (NH_4^+), nitrate (NO_3^-), total nitrogen (TN), and total phosphorus (TP). To support mass balance based nutrient budgeting, sampling from all major inflows and outflows is prioritized. To detect nutrient conditions and processes within the wetland system, surface water samples may also be collected from representative zones or hydrologic features with sufficient standing water (i.e., vernal pools, vegetated areas, interconnected smaller pond-like areas, etc.). Within-wetland surface water sampling points may be stratified across representative hydrologic features (e.g., across pools representing a range of hydroperiods and/or vegetation types) and/or along flow paths within each Project.

A majority of surface water sampling occurs from March through December, with opportunistic sampling for January through February. In Focal Projects, samples are collected at a higher frequency than in Non-focal Projects, generally weekly to monthly, depending on the nature of the Project site and additional logistical considerations. In Non-focal Projects, samples are collected approximately monthly and/or seasonally. Where resources are available, water samples may also be collected by automated samplers, particularly to sample during storms and other hydrologic events. Concurrent with surface water sampling for water chemistry, hand-held sensors are used to measure physicochemical parameters including dissolved oxygen, temperature, specific conductance, and pH.

The Monitoring Program strives to sample at least two hydrologic events per year in all monitored Projects, prioritizing Focal Projects. Project-specific events are described during the Project Characterization phase and described in Project Specific Monitoring Plans. While many hydrologic events are driven by precipitation and storm events causing increased flow rates, there are many other kinds of events. For example, in floodplain Projects an “event” may be defined as an instance when an adjacent river or stream inundates the floodplain Wetland Project to a pre-determined depth and/or extent. In coastal wetlands, events may be defined by seiche activity or when water level control actions are implemented.

Water quality sensors include measures of common physicochemical parameters (dissolved oxygen, pH, conductivity, and temperature), as well as turbidity. At Focal Wetland Projects, water quality sensors are deployed at select concurrent locations as the water quality sampling locations. In Focal Projects, and in Non-focal where resources permit, multiparameter sondes are located at persistently flooded inflows and outflows of the wetlands (when inflows and outflows are present) and if appropriate, the deepest part of the wetland. At both Focal and Non-focal Projects, other sensors, such as turbidity and conductivity sensors, are deployed to characterize water quality conditions along flow paths and within wetland features. Hydrology sensors may likely be deployed at the same locations as water quality sensors but may also be deployed in other wetland locations to monitor hydrology.

Across all monitored Projects, hydrologic data is used to characterize hydrologic descriptors of Wetland Projects including water level, hydroperiod, residence time. In Focal Projects, researchers aim to quantify all major water budget components by combining manual and sensor-based field measurements with mathematical models to estimate water balance, thus supporting nutrient load calculations in mass balance budgeting.

Water Depth

The Monitoring Program measure water depth to monitor hydrology in all monitored Projects. Water depths are measured manually at fixed locations using semi-permanent markers (typically staff gauges) as well as when and where surface water samples are collected. Fixed water depth monitoring locations for manual and sensor-based measurements of water depth are chosen to reflect major hydrologic features of each Project. When a Project contains multiple features that may be subject to different hydrologic drivers, multiple water depth monitoring stations may be established. Staff gages are often installed in the deepest depression area of wetland features such that the base of the staff gage is always underwater (unless it is a temporary wetland). For wetlands with a wide open-water surface, multiple staff gages may be placed at different depths to facilitate measurements during both high-water and drought conditions. In this way, when reading the deeper staff gage is not feasible, the nearest one is visible from the shoreline (Figure 14, USEPA, 2008).

Figure 14. Wetland water level monitoring using staff gages. Using multiple staff gages to determine water levels for wetlands with highly variable stages (credit: USEPA, 2008).

Flow and Discharge

Where persistent or intermittent flow paths exist, especially at key inflows and outflows, every effort is made to measure flow rates to estimate discharge. Where resources are available, high-resolution sensors are installed to monitor flow. In Non-focal Projects where resources do not allow for sensors and in intermittent channel where sensor installation is not a prudent use of resources, crews can manually measure flow rates to develop rating curves and estimate discharge from continuously monitored water depth.

In some locations, researchers may construct devices like flumes and weirs to facilitate flow monitoring. A weir or flume measures surface inflow or outflow water levels at a point of concentrated flow, which are then converted to discharge based on pre-calibrated rating curves. Flow data can also be obtained from USGS gage stations or known pumping rates, if applicable.

For some situations in which instream measurements are not possible, researchers can employ Manning's equation to estimate water velocity and streamflow or discharge (Equation 1).

$$Q = VA = \frac{1.49}{n} AR^{2/3} S^{1/2}$$

Equation 1. Where Q is discharge (cfs), V is the velocity (ft/s), A is the cross-sectional area of the flow (ft²), n is the Manning's roughness coefficient, R is the hydraulic radius (i.e., the ratio of the stream cross-sectional area to the wetted perimeter P , $R=A/P$), and S is the gradient in the total head or water surface slope. Values of Manning's roughness coefficients for channels and floodplains can found in US Geological Survey's guide (Arcement & Schneider, 1989).

Groundwater

To detect groundwater influence, the Monitoring Program installs groundwater monitoring wells at hydrologically important areas, often spatially distributed to capture hydrologic gradients and near locations of surface water sampling. Groundwater monitoring is prioritized in Focal Projects and in Non-focal Projects in which groundwater-surface water interactions are presumed or known to represent a substantial component of the nutrient budget. Comprehensive subsurface characterization helps determine groundwater well locations and depths.

In most instances, researchers install shallow (~1–2.5 m) groundwater monitoring wells screened over their entire depth or bottom 1.5 m to monitor water table levels over their full range of variation. In select locations and when resources permit, nested multi-level piezometers may be installed with screens at different depths, to monitor differences in hydraulic heads and estimate groundwater–surface water exchange rates. Where resources permit, researchers continuously monitor water level within groundwater monitoring wells using continuously logging sensors (specifically, conductivity–temperature–depth, CTD, sensors). In Projects with manually measured groundwater well levels, researchers aim to measure water table levels at least bimonthly from October through February, weekly from March through May, and once a month from June through September (USFWS, 1999).

To characterize nutrient dynamics in groundwater, researchers collect water samples from installed groundwater wells at a similar frequency to surface water sample collection and measure the same suite of dissolved constituents as in surface water samples.

Soil Moisture

To continue to surveil hydrologic conditions in variably inundated locations within Wetland Projects when soils are not flooded, soil moisture sensors are installed in select Projects, and are often co-located with groundwater monitoring and sampling wells.

Weather

Weather stations are installed at Focal Projects to measure key meteorological components of the water budget, specifically: solar radiation, air temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, and wind speed. These data inform estimates of evapotranspiration rates.

Modeling

When sufficient data has been collected in Focal Projects, the Monitoring Program develop fully integrated numerical models capable of simulating surface–subsurface flow and transport processes in a 3-D framework to assist wetland water budget and nutrient removal efficiency calculations. Researchers can see ***Hydrodynamic Modeling*** for more details about the data that informs the model and the modeling approach.

5.3.4 Soil and Sediment Sampling Designs

The quantity and location of soil and sediment sampling points are determined both by the size and heterogeneity of the Project site, as well as cost and accessibility. Soil and sediment sampling, in general, is conducted at each major zone, as identified in Project Characterization and heavily informed by available soil map data. Additionally, soil may be collected along major visible hydrologic or elevation gradients. Generally, surface soils (0–5 cm) are sampled consistently throughout and across all Projects. Where resources allow and where relevant, deeper cores with variable vertical stratification along visible soil horizons and/or at fixed increments may be collected.

Soil sampling frequency and resolution is higher in Focal Projects as compared to Non-focal Projects, but not nearly as frequent as surface water sampling. Soil characteristics are less

temporally variable than water chemistry. Care is taken to prevent over sampling and destruction of the soil at sampling locations.

To assess the rates of key soil nutrient processes, the Monitoring Program employs more costly and labor-intensive techniques in a subset of Focal Projects at lower intensities and frequencies than general soil sampling. Specifically, use intact core incubations, *in situ* deployments of ion exchange resins, and sedimentation markers to measure indices of nutrient processing (e.g., denitrification), sediment–surface water nutrient exchange, and sedimentation.

In general, the intact core flux rates are determined using up to 12 cores per Focal Project, with 3–6 cores per zone or feature, depending on resources, accessibility, and wetland heterogeneity. Zones are selected for intact core incubations and/or resin bag deployment based on dominant hydrological and biogeochemical conditions as indicated by elevation, soil conditions, plant communities etc.,. Additionally, researchers may purposefully select contrasting conditions and/or gradients to inform our understanding of controls over sediment–surface water nutrient exchange rates in different kinds of environments. When resources allow, cores may be collected in each of up to four major seasonal conditions at each location.

Where sedimentation markers are deployed, sedimentation rate measurements are collected once per year at a minimum. Nutrient fluxes using resin bags are deployed in tandem with soil sampling at select zones and features and collected within two to four weeks of deployment.

5.3.5 Plant Community, Biomass, and Nutrient Content Sampling & Frequency

To estimate plant nutrient uptake, storage, and re-mineralization, researchers monitor plant community composition, above- and below-ground biomass, and plant tissue nutrient content in select Focal Projects. Vegetation surveys and sampling are restricted to wetland areas within Project boundaries and any upland areas within Project boundaries, even where restoration activities like prairie and tree plantings have occurred, are not monitored.

Following wetland restorations where significant construction, planting, or seeding occur, vegetation community composition – and therefore nutrient storage capacity – changes rapidly. When resources are adequate, a survey of plant community composition within all wetland areas and sampling of dominant vegetation species for nutrient content occurs annually at peak biomass (roughly July–August) within Focal Projects. Otherwise, plant monitoring may occur on every-other-year rotation.

When vegetation monitoring occurs at a Focal Project, the vegetation crew begins by surveying community composition in quadrat samples distributed randomly within the wetland area. An analysis of vegetation community types observed at the Project then informs plant biomass and tissue nutrient content sampling, stratified randomly within those distinct vegetation communities observed during community composition surveys. Above-ground plant sampling occurs at approximately half the community composition sampling locations and below-ground sampling occurs at approximately one quarter of the locations. When possible, sampling prioritizes the most abundant species in a Project and mono-specific (single species) patches in order to learn more about individual species' contributions to nutrient storage.

Researchers combine plot-level plant composition data with drone imagery to generate an annual map of vegetation community patches for an entire Project. These patch maps help delineate the area each vegetation community covers within a Project. The maps are combined with percent cover, biomass, and plant tissue nutrient content measurements to calculate the mean nutrient storage of a vegetation community and cumulative nutrient storage of all vegetation within a Project at peak biomass. Changes in storage pool year-to-year provide the Monitoring Program with the ability to monitor how nutrients move through wetland storage pools over time.

5.3.6 Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (Drone) Imagery

High-resolution unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) imagery is used for two primary purposes: 1) to map dominant vegetation communities and 2) to collect soil surface elevation data. In addition, drone images support visualization of as-built Projects, particularly when publicly available aerial imagery (e.g., [OGRIP](#), [NAIP](#) or [Google Earth](#)) has not yet been taken of the location after wetland restoration. The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program uses UAVs equipped with multiband imaging in the visible and near-infrared (VIS/NIR).

Drone imagery to map vegetation is collected in coordination with vegetation community surveys in select Focal Projects during the peak plant growing season (August–September). Additional flights are conducted at the remaining Focal Projects once between June and September. When resources allow, additional imagery can be captured in May–June, allowing assessment at a second important time point in the growing season for Focal Projects and allow differences in phenology to be used in classifying vegetation patches. In addition, select Non-focal Projects may be imaged or for visualizing vegetation cover and water inundation.

In situations when UAV data cannot be acquired, multispectral Copernicus Sentinel 2 MSI or Planet Labs' PlanetScope satellite imagery can be used to generate similar products to complement UAV data to investigate open water with emergent vegetation areas, and other phenological driven discrimination of vegetation types. Because of the lower spatial resolution (10 m/pixel via Sentinel 2, 3m/pixel via PlanetScope), the details are different, but they can be used to evaluate the overall extent of inundation and vegetation coverage. The Sentinel-2 and Planet Labs data are available between a weekly and monthly repeat, depending on cloud cover.

Drone imagery for soil surface elevation measurements is taken during leaf-off periods, preferably when variably inundated areas are un-inundated (typically November or December, depending on snowfall).

5.3.7 Mapping Subsurface Geophysical Characteristics

A suite of complementary geophysical mapping techniques can be used to characterize Focal Project soil layers, map inferred soil properties, guide soil sampling and groundwater monitoring locations, and inform models of groundwater flow and hydrologic exchange between the subsurface and surface waters. Geophysical data are integral to quantifying groundwater nutrient load fluxes and improve our estimates of soil nutrient storage pools. The three primary geophysical methods used by the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program are ground penetrating radar (GPR), electromagnetic induction (EMI), and electrical resistance tomography (ERT).

6 Data Management and Quality Control

The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program data collection is carried out by researchers distributed across multiple institutions and includes data types that vary in spatial and temporal extent. The Program's diffuse and diverse data collection requires diligent data management that supports data centralization, assures quality and consistency throughout the data lifecycle, and facilitates comprehensive synthesis of information within and across Wetland Projects. Data collected for the Monitoring Program is managed according to best practices for open data and follow FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles to ensure data integrity and usability. The development and implementation of the data management system for the Monitoring Program is primarily performed by a core data management team led by the Chief Data Manager, with contributions from the Research Coordinator and the various coordinators and technicians within the Monitoring Program. An appointed data curator within each institution, with oversight from the Principal Investigator, is responsible for ensuring proper execution of laboratory-specific quality assurance and quality control processes, and conformance to Program-wide data management standards. Monitoring Program personnel are trained by the Chief Data Manager or core data management team member on pertinent data management and quality workflows at least once every year, or when substantial adjustments are made to the system in place.

The development of the data management and documentation system for the Monitoring Program is ongoing and iterative. The system has adapted to new technologies and/or data collection approaches and has advanced in areas where workflow efficiency needed to be improved. Every effort has been made to implement a system that is equally cohesive and modular, capable of accommodating the flexibility required by a multifaceted, multi-year, and multi-institution environmental monitoring program. As necessary adjustments to monitoring design or data collection approaches occur in the Monitoring Program, the changes and rationale are documented and the data management system is revised accordingly. *This chapter of the Framework describes the foundation of and current (as of June 2024) data management system for the Monitoring Program, including data entry, quality management, storage, and sharing.*

6.1 Controlled Data Entry Systems

The Monitoring Program uses digital data collection forms built in Esri ArcGIS Survey123 to acquire several data types. Digital forms are useful tools for programs of broad temporal and spatial scale because they facilitate controlled, consistent, centralized data collection, and support a high level of complexity and customization. Digital data collection forms achieve four programmatic data management goals:

- Ensure thorough metadata documentation and unique sample identification and tracking.
- Implement comprehensive quality assurance steps to prevent errors.
- Increase efficiency by standardizing data entry and removing data transcription (in lieu of using analog data records only).
- Seamlessly centralize data storage from all data collectors into one common repository.

Digital data collection forms were developed for several data streams, including water and soil sample metadata, *in situ* physicochemical measurements, vegetation community composition and biomass sample metadata, and sensor status tracking. Data collectors use digital forms in the field and laboratory by means of a mobile device and external GPS unit, when applicable. Data collected via the digital forms are stored in a central online database on ArcGIS Online upon submission and harvested daily from the online database via automated workflows into a version-controlled dedicated online repository on the hosting service GitHub.

Digital forms intended for external partners were also developed to fulfill the Monitoring Program's demand for collaboration and assistance beyond our research team. Our primary objective for the publicly available forms is to support the integration of all wetland-related H2Ohio datasets by centralizing data collected at Wetland Projects, facilitating data access and sharing, and employing consistent data entry and quality criteria across a diverse pool of data collectors. Digital forms are iteratively developed to incorporate necessary changes over time, and updated versions are released to data collectors as they become available. A detailed log of form versions is maintained by the core data management team to document bug fixes, enhancements, or substantial changes in each versioned release.

An additional controlled data entry system is in place for datasets that are not recorded via the digital data collection forms. Datasets generated from the chemical analysis of water, soil, and biomass samples for nutrient content are transferred to Program-wide templates in non-proprietary file format after completion of internal laboratory-specific quality control. Cumulative datasets are routinely uploaded by data curators to a dedicated repository on GitHub. The datasets are automatically assessed for proper formatting and completeness, then undergo the automated quality checks that are further described below. Datasets generated by deployable sensors that are not connected to telemetry networks are also manually uploaded by data curators every two months in proprietary and non-proprietary formats to a dedicated repository. Finally, data generated by network-connected sensors that relay live meteorological and physicochemical data to an online dashboard (Ubidots) are harvested daily in non-proprietary format from the online dashboard into a dedicated repository on GitHub via automated workflows.

6.2 Data Quality Management

Data collected and generated by the Monitoring Program should be of known quality and meet the goals and criteria defined within the Data Quality Management Plan. The Data Quality Management Plan has been developed by the core data management team to ensure that all datasets and data products meet quality standards prior to release. Quality assurance (QA) procedures are embedded in data collection steps to minimize errors and ensure the data collected meet defined criteria. Quality control (QC) processes are implemented via automated systems to identify errors on collected data and include near real-time, delayed mode, and human-assisted checks, depending on the data and collection type. The Data Quality Management Plan has been drafted, tested, and implemented in phases since the Monitoring Program's inception, with regular revisions to accommodate for the evolution of data collection workflows and the need for increased efficiency.

Several quality assurance steps are embedded in the controlled data entry systems used to collect metadata and tabular data. The digital data collection forms built on Esri ArcGIS Survey123 include constraints that ensure that all required metadata are complete, sample identifiers are unique and properly formatted, physicochemical measurements are within the logical values for the parameter (e.g., $\text{pH} < 14$) and within the sensor range, among other error checks (e.g., typos). The digital forms also employ prolific use of dropdown menus with predefined value lists (e.g., vegetation species list) to ensure consistent and efficient data entry. While some constraints in the digital forms prevent the data collector from submitting a data entry if a parameter is not met, others are structured to alert the data collector of possible errors but ultimately allows their discretion on whether any correction is necessary. Constraints are continuously adapted and updated to ensure their application is supporting the most up-to-date quality objectives.

All tabular datasets generated by data collectors or deployable sensors are tested against defined data quality requirements to ensure conformance with Monitoring Program standards. Quality-checked datasets contain primary and secondary quality flags for each variable of interest to document the quality status of observations and ensure that data users have pertinent information to apply discretion when analyzing the data. In general, raw tabular data undergo pre-processing steps that merge relevant datasets, perform conversions, ensure consistent formatting, and harmonize legacy data. After pre-processing, the datasets are checked against applicable quality control tests that assess aspects like accuracy, validity, and completeness, and data quality is documented via primary and secondary quality flags. Acceptance criteria vary between Program-wide and laboratory-specific thresholds based on the variable of interest, and are defined using instrument- and expert-defined thresholds. Finally, the quality-checked datasets undergo post-processing steps to prepare the dataset for integration, analysis, synthesis, and release. The pre-processing, quality control, and post-processing steps are automated via a continuous integration system (GitHub Actions) set up in a version-controlled online repository on the hosting service GitHub. By automating these steps, datasets are processed and quality-checked in near real-time, which ultimately shortens the time between data collection, analysis, and sharing. Each step of the data quality workflow is built using Python and YAML (data serialization language) coding scripts that perform specific tasks and connect the series of processes performed on each dataset. All processes in the data quality workflow contain specific logging systems to document completed steps and allows for effective audits and troubleshooting.

The Monitoring Program has identified the Integrated Ocean Observing System (IOOS) Quality Assurance/Quality Control of Real Time Oceanographic Data (QARTOD) program developed by the National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) as a guide for the development of data quality tests for the Monitoring Program. The IOOS QARTOD QC manuals outline up to 11 required and optional QC tests for each variable, with suggestions for order of implementation, reasoning for application, and detailed description of each test. The structure outlined in IOOS QARTOD manuals has been used as the scaffold for the data quality system built specifically for the Monitoring Program. Variations to the methods outlined in the IOOS QARTOD manuals to conform to our data workflows will be thoroughly documented, along with expert- or sensor-defined acceptable value ranges used for each variable. Environmental

variables measured by the Monitoring Program that are not explicitly covered in the IOOS QARTOD methods will follow the QC rigor outlined in the manuals, with adjustments to expert-defined value ranges and the applicability of each QC test based on the variable of interest.

6.3 Data Storage and Backup

6.3.1 *Tabular Data Storage*

All tabular data have been stored in version-controlled online repositories within the hosting service GitHub that holds all proprietary and non-proprietary files, processed datasets, and supports detailed documentation of file changes. The repositories are dedicated exclusively to Monitoring Program data and managed within an organization account for quality checks, code development, workflow implementation, and internal data sharing.

6.3.2 *Non-Tabular Data Storage*

Data generated by the drone and hydrogeophysics specialty crews are inherently different from the tabular datasets derived from other crews. These data are generally large in file size and stored in a variety of formats that can aggregate geospatial or multidimensional information. Both raw and processed drone imagery and mosaics, along with hydrogeophysics files that include a combination of tabular and raster files, are currently (as of June 2024) stored and organized in directories within the Ohio Supercomputer Center (OSC) repository.

6.3.3 *PostgreSQL Database Development*

As of June 2024, a custom-built PostgreSQL database is in early phases of development to permanently store the quality-checked data and allow query and internal access to data. The database will be hosted on the Ohio Supercomputer Center (OSC) and is expected to be operational by the end of 2025. The initial database infrastructure was created in collaboration with the Department of Computer Sciences & Engineering and the Translational Data Analytics Institute at Ohio State University. The Monitoring Program aims to finalize the draft database schemas that have been designed and iteratively adapted to the substantial workflow revisions in the first years (2021 – 2024) of data collection.

6.3.4 *Backup*

Data in the online repositories are backed up weekly using a batch file on task scheduler in a local machine. The data backups constitute the full directory organization and files contained in the repository on the respective date and time. The batch file runs a Python program that was developed to 1) pull all data from the respective GitHub repository and compress it into one zip file, 2) upload the backup files to a cloud file storage (OneDrive), and 3) document backup events via a Data Backup Log that records the date, name of the repository, file size, and upload status to the cloud service. Every other month, cumulative backups are manually uploaded by the core data management team to the OSC project storage space for long-term retention. The data storage on OSC provides an additional layer of data recovery as project spaces are backed up daily through OSC.

6.4 Data Sharing, Public Access, and Reuse Policies

The Monitoring Program aims to publicly release data annually alongside or shortly following the publication of the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Annual Report. Data releases supplement the summarized information provided in Annual Reports, which contain contextualized and interpreted statements about the data and aim to reach broader audiences. The data releases are intended to provide complete datasets to audiences that are interested in using Monitoring Program data for further analyses and research, primarily the scientific community.

Datasets will be considered for public release after undergoing internal and Program-wide quality checks and meeting all the prerequisites outlined below. Full datasets will be embargoed for up to two years from when they are summarized and released in the Annual Progress Report to allow for the development of data products, interpretations, and publications by the Monitoring Program (e.g., data summarized in the 2023 Annual Progress Report, which is published in 2024, will be publicly available in 2026). After the embargo is lifted, datasets will be made publicly accessible via the Environmental Data Initiative (EDI) Data Portal, which is an NSF-funded data commons that aims to preserve environmental data for open and reproducible science. Datasets and accompanying metadata will be fully citable with a digital object identifier (DOI) and licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0).

Prerequisites for Data Release:

- Quality control tests identified, implemented, and described in written documentation.
- Quality flags identified, implemented, and described in written documentation.
- Acceptance criteria for each data type identified, implemented, and described in written documentation (ranges, thresholds, etc.).
- Metadata files fully written containing all pertinent details about released datasets.
- Datasets must have been pre-processed and quality checked and contain quality flags assigned to each observation.
- Data packages must be versioned, assigned a DOI, and shared accordingly.

Data releases will include tabular datasets containing vegetation community composition, sample metadata (e.g., geolocation) and nutrient concentration for water, soil, and biomass samples, and physicochemical/meteorological measurements from handheld, deployable, and network-connected sensors. Datasets will be released cumulatively, by data type, and in full (i.e., including flagged data). Data users can use information about flag codes and metadata to process and interpret the data according to their own research or analysis needs. Non-tabular data products generated by the Monitoring Program (e.g., hydrogeophysics, 3-D hydrodynamic model outputs, drone imagery, other geospatial products), will not be included in initial data releases but may be made available upon request when appropriate. Computational programs or coding scripts developed for data processing will be shared gradually on the EDI Data Portal as stable versions are developed and tested.

7 References

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